

2024 ANNUAL REPORT

Submitted to:

Utah State Legislature
and
Uintah Special Service District 1

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Acknowledgments

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Site access, electricity, and/or equipment at some of our monitoring stations are provided by the Utah Division of Air Quality, Scout Energy Partners, Koda Resources, and the Bureau of Land Management.

Many energy companies have provided data and access to oil and gas facilities for our work. Marc and Debbie Bingham, the namesakes of the Bingham Research Center, provided initial funds to establish the Center and its facilities. We are grateful for the support of each of these groups, and the continuing support of the administrators and staff at the Uintah Basin Campus, Statewide Campuses, and President Elizabeth Cantwell and her administrative team at Utah State University.

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Executive Summary

The Bingham Research Center was established in 2010 through a generous donation from the Marc and Debbie Bingham Family.

Mission of the Bingham Research Center

The mission of Utah State University's Bingham Research Center is to conduct high-quality academic research that can be used by industry, government, and the public to develop efficient and effective solutions to environmental problems. The Center focuses on research that benefits Utah and the Uinta Basin, but scientists at the Center carry out projects around the world and strive for their work to be globally relevant.

Purpose of this Report

This report details the activities undertaken by the Bingham Research Center over the past twelve months. The report focuses on winter ozone research, as this is a core research area for the Center, and it serves as an annual report to the Utah Legislature and Uintah Special Service District 1, the primary funders of the Center's winter ozone research. The report also contains information about other projects funded by other entities, the Center's goals, and performance. This and past reports are available at:

<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/papers-and-reports>. The Center's Management Plan is available here: <https://usu.box.com/s/877z4o8nwynu3uwcze8uxi8jaant7auw>.

Background Information about Wintertime Ozone

Ozone negatively impacts respiratory health, especially for those with lung diseases. During wintertime temperature inversion episodes, ozone in the Uinta Basin sometimes increases to levels that exceed the standard of 70 ppb set by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). Because of this, the portions of Uintah and Duchesne counties have been designated as nonattainment areas in the past.

The Uinta Basin is one of only two places in the world known to routinely experience wintertime ozone exceeding EPA standards (Wyoming's Upper Green River Basin is the other). Ozone forms in the atmosphere from reactions involving oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) and organic compounds, and the majority of NO_x and organic compound emissions in the Uinta Basin are from oil and gas development. Inversion conditions trap these pollutants near ground level, increasing their concentrations and allowing them to generate ozone. The unique mix of pollutants during inversion episodes in the Uinta Basin leads to the formation of wintertime ozone, in contrast to the fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) pollution that is prevalent during winters on the Wasatch Front.

The number of ozone exceedance days and concentrations of ozone that occur each year are closely tied to meteorology. Years with persistent snow cover and high barometric pressure tend to have more days with strong winter inversions and high ozone. In the absence of snow cover and winter inversions, ozone concentrations in the Basin are similar to those in other rural, high-elevation locations around the western United States. Changes in emissions of organic compounds and NO_x can also impact ozone levels. This past winter 2023-2024, saw no days that exceeded the EPA standards. Because of this data, the EPA is considering designating the Uinta Basin as compliant.

Because wintertime ozone is relatively new to science, some aspects of the meteorology, chemistry, and emissions that allow ozone to form during winter are still poorly understood. Federal and state agencies are required by law to promulgate regulations that reduce ozone-forming emissions in the Uinta Basin. These regulations will mostly target the local oil and gas industry, which contributes to the majority of the Basin's economy. Scientific research to better elucidate the causes and characteristics of winter ozone can help industry and regulators craft emissions reductions that maximize effectiveness and minimize costs to the local industry and economy. Since 2010, we (scientists at the Bingham Research Center) have conducted research to improve the understanding of winter ozone in the Uinta Basin.

A cumulative summary of all significant research findings that relate to Uinta Basin air quality from 2010 through the present is available here:

<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/cumulative-research-summary>.

Bingham Research Center Productivity

The scientists, technicians, and student employees have been busy this past year. They have had thirteen papers published in scientific journals. Center scientists and staff made 23 presentations at local groups, regional, national, and international conferences. Three PhD candidates are pursuing their research under the guidance of Bingham Research scientists. Please see the section on 2024 Performance for specific details.

Colleen Jones, PhD, was promoted to Lead Scientist and Research Associate Professor. John R. Lawson, PhD, was promoted to Research Assistant Professor.

Bingham Research scientists are sought after to collaborate with colleagues outside the university. Currently, Center scientists have collaborated with others on grants from the Department of Energy (University of Utah, Brigham Young University, Stanford University, University of Nevada—Reno, IBM). The EPA (Utah Radon Lab, USU's Office of Sustainability, Tri-County Health, Healthy Communities of Northeastern Utah, USU's Transforming Communities Institute), and the National Science Foundation (BYU).

2024 Performance

This section contains information about our performance on overall goals for Uinta Basin air quality research and performance for annual project objectives for the 2024 reporting period. Our management plan, which describes our group's overall goals and objectives, is available at: <https://usu.box.com/s/877z4o8nwynu3uwcze8uxj8jaant7auw>.

Research Output

The basic outcomes of our research are publications and presentations that describe our work and make it available to other academics, stakeholders, and the public. The Bingham Research team had 13 reports accepted for publication in academic journals. All the peer-reviewed publications and significant technical reports are available on our website at <https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/papers-and-reports>.

Peer-reviewed Publications

1. Lawson, J.R. and Lyman, S.N., 2024. A Preliminary Fuzzy Inference System for Predicting Atmospheric Ozone in an Intermountain Basin. *Air*, 2(3), pp.337-361. <https://doi.org/10.3390/air2030020>.
2. Jones, C., Tran, H., Tran, T. and Lyman, S., 2024. Assimilating Satellite-Derived Snow Cover and Albedo Data to Improve 3-D Weather and Photochemical Models. *Atmosphere*, 15(8), p.954.
3. Ghimire, S., Lebo, Z.J., Murphy, S., Rahimi, S. and Tran, T., 2023. Simulations of winter ozone in the Upper Green River basin, Wyoming, using WRF-Chem. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 23(16), pp.9413-9438.
4. Lee, C.F., Elgiar, T., David, L.M., Wilmot, T.Y., Reza, M., Hirshorn, N., McCubbin, I.B., Shah, V., Lin, J.C., Lyman, S. and Hallar, A.G., 2024. Elevated Tropospheric Iodine over the Central Continental United States: Is Iodine a Major Oxidant of Atmospheric Mercury? *Geophysical Research Letters*, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024GL109247>.
5. Derry, E.J., Elgiar, T.R., Wilmot, T.Y., Hoch, N.W., Hirshorn, N.S., Weiss-Penzias, P., Lee, C.F., Lin, J.C., Hallar, A.G., Volkamer, R. and Lyman, S.N., 2024. Elevated oxidized mercury in the free troposphere: Analytical advances and application at a remote continental mountaintop site. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 24(16), pp.9615-9643.
6. Gačnik, J., Lyman, S., Dunham-Cheatham, S.M. and Gustin, M.S., 2024. Limitations and insights regarding atmospheric mercury sampling using gold. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 1319, p.342956.
7. Gustin, M.S., Dunham-Cheatham, S.M., Lyman, S., Horvat, M., Gay, D.A., Gačnik, J., Gratz, L., Kempkes, G., Khalizov, A., Lin, C.J. and Lindberg, S.E., 2024. Measurement of Atmospheric Mercury: Current Limitations and Suggestions for Paths Forward. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 58(29), pp.12853-12864.

8. Elgiar, T.R., Lyman, S.N., Andron, T.D., Gratz, L., Hallar, A.G., Horvat, M., Vijayakumaran Nair, S., O’Neil, T., Volkamer, R. and Živković, I., 2024. Traceable Calibration of Atmospheric Oxidized Mercury Measurements. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 58(24), 10706–10716.
9. Gustin, M.S., Dunham-Cheatham, S.M., Allen, N., Choma, N., Johnson, W., Lopez, S., Russell, A., Mei, E., Magand, O., Dommergue, A. and Elgiar, T., 2023. Observations of the chemistry and concentrations of reactive Hg at locations with different ambient air chemistry. *Science of The Total Environment*, 904, p.166184.
10. Cope, E.M., Ketcherside, D.T., Jin, L., Tan, L., Mansfield, M., Jones, C., Lyman, S., Jaffe, D. and Hu, L., 2024. Sources of atmospheric volatile organic compounds during the salt lake regional smoke, ozone and aerosol study (SAMOZA) 2022. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 129(17), e2024JD041640.
11. Lawson, J.R., Potvin, C.K. and Nelson, K., 2024. Decoding the Atmosphere: Optimising Probabilistic Forecasts with Information Gain. *Meteorology*, 3(2), pp.212-231.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/meteorology3020010>.
12. Jaffe, D.A., Ninneman, M., Nguyen, L., Lee, H., Hu, L., Ketcherside, D., Jin, L., Cope, E., Lyman, S., Jones, C. and O’Neil, T., 2024. Key results from the salt lake regional smoke, ozone, and aerosol study (SAMOZA). *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association*, 74(3), pp.163-180.
13. Stratman, D. R., N. Yussouf, C. A. Kerr, B. C. Matilla, J. R. Lawson, and Y. Wang, 2024: Testing stochastic and perturbed parameter methods in an experimental 1-km Warn-on-Forecast System using NSSL’s phased-array radar observations. *Mon. Weather Rev.*, 152, 433–454,
<https://doi.org/10.1175/mwr-d-23-0095.1>.

Reports

1. Lyman S., Jones C., Lawson L., Mansfield M., David L., O’Neil T., Holmes B., 2023. 2023 Annual Report: Bingham Research Center. Utah State University, Vernal, Utah.
<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/files/reports/BinghamCenter2023AnnualReport.pdf> and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13999275>.
2. Lyman S., Lin J., Tran H., 2024. Top-down Estimates of Emissions from Oil and Gas Production in the Uinta Basin: Final Project Report. Utah State University, Vernal, Utah.
https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/files/reports/Topdowninventory_finalreport_FINAL1.pdf.
3. Lawson, J. R., 2024: Communicating risk with possibility, not probability. arXiv [stat.AP], <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.21664>.
4. Lawson, J. R., J. E. Trujillo-Falcón, D. M. Schultz, M. L. Flora, K. H. Goebbert, S. N. Lyman, C. K. Potvin, and A. J. Stepanek, 2024: Pixels and predictions: Potential of GPT-4V in meteorological imagery analysis and forecast communication. arXiv [cs.CL], <http://arxiv.org/abs/2404.15166>.

Presentations

1. Elgiar T., Lyman S., Gratz L., David L., Volkamer R., Hallar G., December 2023, GEOS-Chem produces much less atmospheric oxidized mercury than calibrated measurements. AGU Fall Meeting, San Francisco, California.
2. Gratz L., Derry E., Lyman S., Elgiar T., Wilmot T., Volkamer R., December 2023. Determining the origins of ambient oxidized mercury at a continental mountaintop site in the western U.S. AGU Fall Meeting, San Francisco, California.
3. Lyman S., February 2024. Our efforts to develop methods for oxidized mercury compounds. PittCon, San Diego, California.
4. Lyman S., March 2024. Uinta Basin Air Quality. Ute Indian Tribe Education Department, Fort Duchesne, Utah.
5. Lawson, J. R., M. J. Davies, and S. N. Lyman, March 2024: The Uinta Basin Snow Shadow: 2022/23 & 2023/24. 8th Science for Solutions Conference, Ogden, Utah, 28 March 2024. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13937073>
6. Dhar L., Lyman S., March 2024, Understanding the Complexity of Winter Ozone Formation by Analyzing Different Chemical Mechanisms in a Box Model, Air Quality Science for Solution Conference, Ogden, Utah.
7. Lyman S., May 2024. Air Quality in the Uinta Basin. Vernal Area Chamber of Commerce, Vernal, Utah.
8. Lyman S., May 2024. Methane emissions panel. Wilkes Climate Summit, Salt Lake City Utah.
9. Lyman S., July 2024. Introduction to the Bingham Research Center. Utah Methane Coalition, Utah (online).
10. Lawson, J. R., M. J. Davies, July 2024: Fuzzy Winter-Ozone Predictions. 21st Conference on Mountain Meteorology, American Meteorological Society, Boise, ID.
11. Lyman S., July 2024. Introduction to the Uinta Basin Ozone Working Group. Utah Division of Oil, Gas and Mining Uinta Basin Collaborative Meeting, Duchesne, Utah.
12. Lyman S., Elgiar T., July 2024. Photochemical models are unable to simulate high oxidized mercury measured in the western United States. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
13. Lyman S., Elgiar T., July 2024. Advancing permeation tube-based mercury calibration. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
14. Dunham-Cheatham S., Lyman S., Lown L., Gacnik J., O'Neil T., Gustin M., July 2024. Toward a GC-MS method for quantification and characterization of ambient gaseous oxidized mercury compounds. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.

15. Gacnik J., Dunham-Cheatham S., Lyman S., Gustin M., July 2024. Particulate-bound mercury sampling using membrane materials: biases due to adsorption of gaseous oxidized mercury. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
16. Gacnik J., Dunham-Cheatham S., Lyman S., Gustin M., July 2024. Gold sampling for atmospheric mercury analysis: insights and limitations. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
17. Gustin M., Dunham-Cheatham S., Lyman S., July 2024. Workshop Results: Measurement of Atmospheric Mercury: Assessment of new measurement and calibration methods and development of a path forward. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
18. O'Neil T., Lyman S., Elgiar T., Zager K., July 2024. Tips and Tricks of the trade: Building instrumentation for atmospheric mercury. International Conference on Mercury as a Global Pollutant, Capetown, South Africa.
19. Lyman S., September 2024. Uinta Basin air quality update. Uinta Basin Energy Summit, Vernal, Utah.
20. Dhar L., Lyman S., October 2024, Influence of Chemical Mechanism on Carbonyl and Ozone Formation During Winter, 23 Annual CMAS Conference, Chapel Hill, North Carolina.
21. Lawson, J.R., November 2024. AI is a wonderful innovation, but can we trust it? Science Unwrapped, Utah State Univ., Logan, Utah.
22. Lawson, J.R., November 2024. Fuzzy pollution predictions: communicating risk as possibility, not probability. Applied Math colloquium series, Utah State Univ., Logan, Utah.
23. Lawson, J.R., November 2024. CLYFAR (AI ozone prediction model) tutorial. Lunch & Learn Series, Uinta Basin Working Group, Utah.
24. Allred, J., Jones, C. P., November 2024. Aerial Imagery for Vegetation Monitoring Post-Wildfire. Utah Watershed Restoration Indicative Northeastern Region Annual Meeting, San Antonio, Texas.

Funding

The Bingham Research Center received \$685,217 in grants and contracts, \$50,000 in gifts, \$400,000 in appropriations from the Utah Legislature, and \$26,980 in endowment disbursements in the past 12 months for a total of \$1,162,197 (Table 1).

Table 1. Funding received by the Bingham Research Center in the past twelve months.

Project	Funder	Type	Start	End	Amount
Uintah Basin Ozone Study	Uintah Special Service District 1	Contract	2024	2024	\$250,000
Air and Water Innovation Grant Management	Utah Governor's Office of Economic Development	Grant	2024	2026	\$30,000
Cattail Control Management Strategies on Utah's Public Lands	Utah Public Lands Initiative	Grant	2024	2025	\$43,011
The Uinta-Piceance Basin Carbon Management and Community Engagement Partnership	Department of Energy	Grant	2024	2027	\$362,206
Funding for new gas chromatograph/mass spectrometer	Marriner S. Eccles Foundation	Gift	2024	2024	\$50,000
Uinta Basin Ozone Study	Utah Legislature	Appropriation	2024	2025	\$400,000
Anadarko student research endowment	Anadarko Petroleum	Endowment disbursement	2024	2025	\$26,980

We have received \$15,148,455 in funding between 2011 and the present, including \$11,269,286 in funding for research specifically related to Uinta Basin air quality. Figure 1 shows the funding we have received, organized by year and type of funding source. In the figure, funds are allocated to the year during which they were first awarded, not the years in which they were spent.

Figure 1. Funding awarded to our research group from 2011 to the present, categorized by type of funding source. For grants and contracts, the entire amount of funding awarded is shown in the first year of the award, even though a portion of those funds may have been spent in subsequent years.

Figure 2 shows a breakdown of our team’s total funding since 2011 by source type: 35% of our funding has come from federal government sources. 32% has come from the state of Utah. 25% has come from local government (entities within Uintah County). 2% and 2% have come from the Ute Indian Tribe and

the State of Wyoming, respectively. 4% has come from private companies, and less than 0.1% has come from foreign entities.

Figure 2. All funding sources for our research team from 2011 to the present.

Figure 3 shows a breakdown of funding for work specifically for projects related to Uinta Basin air quality. Compared to our research funding, a greater part of our winter-ozone-specific research has come from the state of Utah (43%) and local government (35%), while less has come from federal government agencies (20%).

Figure 3. Sources of funding for our research team for Uinta Basin air quality projects from 2011 to the present.

Since our inception, The Bingham Research Center has received funding from the following entities, ranked in order of the total amount of funding received (endowment disbursement, rather than original endowment gift amount, is used in the case of Anadarko Petroleum):

- Uintah Special Service District 1 (formerly Uintah Impact Mitigation Special Service District)
- Utah State Legislature
- National Science Foundation
- Department of Energy
- USTAR
- Utah Division of Air Quality
- Department of Defense
- Bureau of Land Management
- State of Wyoming
- Ute Indian Tribe
- USTAR Energy Research Triangle
- PacifiCorp
- Utah Division of Wildlife Resources
- Anadarko Petroleum
- Utah Division of Wildlife Resources
- National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration
- Dalbo Holdings Inc.
- Marriner S. Eccles Foundation
- Utah Public Lands Initiative
- SITLA
- Chevron Refinery
- Deseret Power
- Utah Governor's Office of Economic Development
- Environmental Protection Agency
- Dominion Energy
- UCAIR
- Simplot Phosphates LLC
- Big West Oil
- Nanjing University
- TriCounty Health

Student Involvement and Training

Anadarko Student Fellowship

A generous endowment from Anadarko Petroleum Corporation provides funds for students to participate in Uinta Basin air quality research (<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/student-fellowship>). The following students have received help from this program and other sources of funding for student research during 2024.

- Brant Holmes has worked with us since May 2021. He has participated in field measurements of oil and gas emissions and is now working to understand how organic compounds in the air interact with snowpack. Brant received an associate's degree from USU in spring 2024.

- Rachel Merrell has worked with us since April 2023. She developed and tested instrumentation for atmospheric mercury in the laboratory and is now analyzing a dataset of wintertime pollutants in the Uinta Basin while pursuing her education at USU's Logan campus.

- Loknath Dhar has worked with us since May 2023. He is a PhD student in USU's Chemistry and Biochemistry Department and is based in Logan. Loknath is researching the chemical pathways that lead to secondary formaldehyde formation during wintertime ozone episodes and how chemical mechanisms used in photochemical models represent those pathways.

- KarLee Zager has worked with us since August 2023. KarLee is pursuing a bachelor's degree in biology at the USU Vernal campus. She is involved in ozone measurement and development and testing of atmospheric mercury instrumentation.

- Justin Allred worked with the Bingham Research Center as an undergraduate and now is pursuing a PhD in Soil Science with Colleen Jones. He is using drone-based multispectral imaging to evaluate the effectiveness of wildfire reclamation techniques.

- Lisa Boyd is pursuing a PhD in Ecology with Colleen Jones and is employed at the Vernal office of the Bureau of Land Management. She is studying the life cycle of endangered plants and ecological reclamation.

- Michael Davies has worked with us since early 2024. He is an undergraduate student at the USU Vernal campus and is working on meteorological data analysis.

- Elspeth Montague is a high school senior at Uintah High School. She started working with us in early 2024 developing web materials to display real-time and forecast air quality information.

- Tristan Coxson is a high school senior at Uintah High School. He started working with us in early 2024 on laboratory analysis and instrumentation.

All Students and Postdoctoral Researchers

These are the students and postdoctoral researchers who have worked at the Bingham Research Center. The year the person first worked at the Center is also listed.

1. Emily Smith, undergraduate, 2012
2. Chad Mangum, undergraduate, 2013
3. Cathy Crawford, undergraduate, 2013
4. Jordan Evans, undergraduate, 2013
5. Trevor O'Neil, undergraduate, 2013
6. Trang Tran, postdoctoral researcher, 2013
7. Huy Tran, postdoctoral researcher, 2014

8. Colleen Jones, postdoctoral researcher, 2015
9. Cody Watkins, master's student, 2014
10. Tate Shorthill, undergraduate, 2014
11. Tanner Allen, undergraduate, 2014
12. Lena Morgan, undergraduate, 2015
13. Felito Martinez, undergraduate, 2015
14. Sheree Meyer, graduate, 2015
15. Eric Hacking, undergraduate, 2016
16. Sandra Young, undergraduate, 2017
17. Justin Allred, undergraduate and graduate, 2017
18. Makenzie Holmes, undergraduate, 2018
19. Tyler Elgiar, undergraduate and graduate, 2018
20. Krystal White, undergraduate, 2019
21. Brant Holmes, undergraduate, 2020
22. Keirra Tolbert, undergraduate, 2021
23. Jackson Liesik, undergraduate, 2021
24. Davis Smuin, undergraduate, 2021
25. Lisa Boyd, graduate, 2022
26. Kristin Miller, undergraduate, 2023
27. Rachel Merrell, undergraduate, 2023
28. Loknath Dhar, graduate, 2023
29. KarLee Zager, undergraduate, 2023
30. Michael Davies, undergraduate, 2024
31. Elspeth Montague, high school, 2024
32. Tristan Coxson, high school, 2024

Data Management, Quality, and Dissemination

Data Management

As described in our management plan, all measurement data and notes we have generated during the reporting period have been stored on a cloud-based data storage server, with regular backups to local, removable hard drives. We stored all instrument maintenance, calibration, and repair information within this archival structure. We used established standard operating procedures for our work. These are publicly available here:

https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/team_pages/standard-operating-procedures.

Atmospheric Data Quality

Table 2 shows a summary of data quality results for ambient air measurements we collected during 2024. The maximum uptime possible for most measurements shown in the table is approximately 95% due to maintenance and calibration periods.

Table 2. Data quality summary for ozone, oxides of nitrogen (NO_x), carbon monoxide (CO), and organic compound data collected during 2022-23. Results are shown as averages ± 95% confidence intervals for all locations at which the indicated measurements were collected (confidence intervals are shown if the number of data points is three or more). For a list of measurements collected and sites of collection, Percent uptime indicates the percentage of the measurement period for which valid measurements were obtained. NMHC indicates non-methane hydrocarbons. N/A means not applicable.

Measurement	Zero calib. (ppb)	Span calib. (% recov.)	Percent uptime
Ozone	-0.4 ± 0.7	100 ± 2	93 ± 10
NO	-0.0 ± 0.0	100 ± 0	89 ± 19
NO _x (NO calib.)	-0.2 ± 0.1	99 ± 1	89 ± 19
NO _y (NO calib.)	-0.4 ± 0.4	98 ± 1	91
NO _x (GPT calib.)	N/A	105 ± 1	89 ± 19
NO _y (GPT calib.)	N/A	97 ± 1	91
CO	-20 ± 19	99 ± 3	97
Methane	33 ± 11	100 ± 0	68
Total NMHC	66 ± 29	103 ± 1	68
Speciated NMHC	0.1 ± 0.0	100 ± 0	94
Speciated Carbonyls	0.0 ± 0.0	98 ± 0	94
PM _{2.5} (BAM)	N/A	N/A	97

Data Dissemination

We have uploaded the winter ozone dataset for the most recent winter and an updated air chemistry and meteorology dataset for the Roosevelt, Castle Peak, and Horsepool monitoring stations to the data access page of our website, <https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/data-access>. We have also updated speciated organic compound data on the same web page.

During the year, we gave meteorological and chemical datasets we collected to regulators, environmental consultants, and energy companies for use in their own analyses.

Outcomes from Annual Air Quality Project Objectives

We identified project goals for the current reporting period in Section 20 of our previous annual report, which is available at:

<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/files/reports/BinghamCenter2023AnnualReport.pdf>.

In Table 3 we report on any discrepancies between planned work and actual outcomes for each of the project objectives outlined in the 2023 annual report.

Table 3. Outcomes of annual project objectives for the current reporting period.

OBJECTIVE	OUTCOMES
Priority 1: Air Chemistry	
Operate air quality monitoring stations	We completed this objective for winter 2023-24. We will continue the operation of these stations for the coming winter.
Continue Investigation of Carbonyl Fluxes at the Air-snow Interface	Measurements for this objective are complete, but we are still analyzing the data we obtained. We expect to release a report in early 2025.
Investigate Ozone Formation in Summertime Wildfire Smoke	We set up a summertime measurement system at the Roosevelt monitoring station as planned for this project. We collected several days of speciated organic compound measurements in smokey and non-smokey periods, and we are currently analyzing the data. We will continue this analysis in the coming year and may collect measurements during summer 2025 if the Roosevelt site again experiences significant wildfire smoke.
Priority 2: Air Quality Modeling	
Improve WRF Simulations of Uinta Basin Winter Inversions	We contributed to a paper published on adding noise to WRF forecasts to improve forecasts. However, Further work using WRF was paused due to concern that AI-based weather models were progressing much faster as frontier science. This caused a change of priorities, weighting the forecast-system objective heavier. We will return to WRF simulations in 2025 as part of a U.S. Department of Energy grant on modeling the air quality impacts of carbon sequestration. The National Weather Service is currently changing national weather-forecast models and this new generation, freely available, requires further analysis of Basin weather for evidence earlier shortcomings have improved. This would motivate a return to this Priority to reassess previous findings.
Develop a System for Quantitative Winter Ozone Forecasts	We have produced an operational first version of our ozone-prediction model, named Clyfar. Its prototype is described in a recent paper, and we will display forecasts on a new UBAIR website for the upcoming 2024-25 Ozone Alert season. This system does not use WRF forecasts. Instead, we utilize available NOAA forecasts and use a rule-based form of artificial intelligence to produce ozone predictions. We will develop version 2 of Clyfar in 2025 ready for that year’s Ozone Alert, adding more AI elements that learn from earlier forecast accuracy.
Box Model Investigation of the Impact of Chemical Mechanisms on Simulations of Winter Ozone	We have completed this work and are currently preparing our findings for publication. We will continue this work with the CMAQ 3D photochemical model in the coming year.

Priority 3: Emissions	
Establish a Method for Monthly Basin-wide Pollutant Emissions Estimates	This work is underway. We are using the Integrated Methane Inversion system (https://imi.seas.harvard.edu/) to ascertain Uinta Basin-wide methane emissions and determine organic compound and NO _x emissions from ambient air correlations. We will have the first emission results from 2019 through 2024 in early 2025.
Development of Methods to Determine Oil Storage Tank Emission Factors in the Uinta Basin	This work is underway. We completed sample collection in November 2023. Lab analysis took much longer than expected but is complete as of September 2024. We have completed a statistical analysis of the laboratory data, and Birol Dindaruk at University of Houston is now performing equation of state modeling. We expect this project to be completed in mid-2025.
Drone-based Measurement of Emissions from Oil and Gas Sources	This is a multi-year objective. We have built the drone-based methane measurement system and tested it, and it is working properly. The next steps are to build a computer program to process the drone system data into emissions measurements, and then to test the entire system against known methane emission rates. At that point, we will be ready to conduct real emissions measurements in the field. We expect to be ready for this in mid-2025.
Priority 4: Stakeholder Engagement	
Operate ubair.usu.edu website to display map-based, real-time air quality information to the public	We completed this goal for the reporting period. We are building a new real-time website.
Operate the Ozone Alert program	We completed this objective for the reporting period.
Uinta Basin Ozone Working Group	We completed this objective for the reporting period. More about the working group can be found at https://www.usu.edu/basinozonegroup/ .

Stakeholder Engagement

The mission of the Bingham Research Center is to generate knowledge and provide information that helps stakeholders (industry, regulators, and others) to make better decisions that will reduce emissions in the Uinta Basin. Thus, we strive to engage stakeholders in our research process to clarify and utilize the data we produce.

2024 Stakeholder Engagement Activities

Ozone Alert Program

At the request of oil and gas industry representatives and with input from the Utah Division of Air Quality, TriCounty Health, and several oil and gas companies, we created a program in 2017 to alert oil and gas companies when we expect high winter ozone.

The program includes a web page (<https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/ozone-alert>) to describe the program and allow individuals to receive alerts. We collect their name, email address, and place of business.

We send everyone on the list an email when we identify a possible local ozone formation. We forecast if an ozone episode extends longer than expected and when episodes end or are expected to end. We attempt to forecast ozone episodes up to six days in advance. The purpose of this program is to provide users with information that allows them to reduce ozone-forming pollution when it matters most.

Winter 2023-24 had zero days with ozone exceeding the EPA standard of 70 ppb. There were some heavy snow events, but air temperatures were too high to support a snowpack after a heavy snowfall. One snowfall did lead to a weak inversion (where cold air begins to stagnate at the Basin floor, trapping pollution), but the snow melted before ozone levels built substantially. Periods during which we alerted subscribers that high ozone levels were likely are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Time series of the highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone the site observed at any monitoring site in the Uinta Basin during winter 2023-24. The EPA ozone standard is shown as a red dashed line. Periods during which USU issued ozone alerts are shown as grey shading.

The program currently has 174 subscribers, with 41% from the energy industry, 23% are affiliated with government entities, 20% are members of the local public, 11% are academics, 2% are representatives of the media, and 1% are from environmental groups.

Uinta Basin Ozone Working Group

In 2018 we coordinated with individuals from government, industry, and environmental advocacy organizations to organize the Uinta Basin Ozone Working Group. The purpose of this group is to determine and promote actions that will reduce wintertime ozone in the Uinta Basin. The group’s website is: <https://basinozonegroup.usu.edu>. Marc Mansfield served as the group’s facilitator and led its steering committee through March 2024. When Marc retired from work at USU, Seth Lyman assumed this role in March 2024. Seth Lyman manages the group’s website and is responsible for group communications, with assistance from Michael Davies. Our team regularly gives presentations to the group about the science of wintertime ozone and actively participates in all working group meetings. The group’s website provides agendas for the meetings and links to presentations given.

Websites

- ubair.usu.edu, our real-time air quality data website, has hundreds of unique users in thousands of sessions every year.
- Our main website, <https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch> and the ozone working group website, <https://www.usu.edu/basinozonegroup>, had hundreds of unique visitors over the reporting period.

Information and Data Sharing

- We gave dozens of presentations to many different stakeholder groups during the reporting period. Please see the Performance Report Section for a list of all presentations.
- We provided our annual report, specific project reports, report summaries, and datasets to members of our stakeholder committee and others in government and industry upon request.
- We have made updated datasets available at: <https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/data-access>.
- We have made all our project reports and peer-reviewed papers publicly available at: <https://www.usu.edu/binghamresearch/papers-and-reports>.
- We make Python and other code we develop for our research available on GitHub at <https://github.com/Bingham-Research-Center>.

Community Outreach and Service

- John Lawson, KarLee Zager, and Michael Davies served as judges at the Uintah School District's middle school science fair in January 2024 and gave the new Bingham Research Center Award for the fair [to Cameron DeBerard](#).
- Seth Lyman is serving on the [Advisory Board for Uinta Basin CarbonSAFE](#), a project to explore carbon capture and storage options in the Uinta Basin.
- John Lawson participated in USU's public-facing science presentation series [Science Unwrapped](#) in November 2024 in Logan, Utah.
- Seth Lyman served as a judge for the [Utah Petroleum Association's Environmental Leadership Awards](#) and presented the awards at the Association's annual meeting in March 2024.
- Seth Lyman was appointed to the [Board of Trustees for Healthy Communities of Northeastern Utah](#) in October 2024.
- Colleen Jones, Trevor O'Neil, John Lawson, and Seth Lyman participated in [USU-Uintah Basin's STEAM Expo](#) for Uinta Basin middle school students in October 2024. They staffed interactive displays with air quality and drone themes.
- Seth Lyman has served on the [Board of Directors for the Utah Clean Air Partnership \(UCAIR\)](#) since 2021.

Use of Our Air Quality Research by Stakeholders

These individuals and agencies use our research, excluding reports and formal presentations, which are reported in the Performance Report Section. A complete list of all stakeholder uses of our research is available at: <https://usu.box.com/s/1k70hyz1dgca2kr9zuynz0locogd9uti>.

- The Environmental Protection Agency cited industry participation in the Bingham Center’s Ozone Alert Program as evidence of progress on atmospheric emissions that allowed them to [accept a second extension of the Uinta Basin’s ozone attainment date](#). This action will very likely result in the Uinta Basin being officially declared in attainment of the EPA ozone standard (it has been in nonattainment since 2018).
- The Utah Petroleum Association cited our research in [their comments on the EPA proposed action to accept the second extension of the Uinta Basin’s ozone attainment date](#).
- The Utah Department of Health and Human Services used data and the expertise of the Bingham Research Center in a study of asthma prevalence and causes in the Uinta Basin region. The study will be released publicly in 2025.

Media Appearances

The following are news articles from the reporting period that mention our work. A complete list of media mentions of our research is available at:

<https://usu.box.com/s/5s0busf524npd935mqfecsnvhn4cep52>.

- 2024. USU and You with John Lawson. KVEL radio (two appearances).
- 2024. [Bingham Research Center receives grant to study carbon capture and storage](#). Carbon Capture Journal. Also see [basinnow.com](#).
- 2024. [Utah’s air quality has been harming your health for years, but tourism is now in the crossfire](#). Salt Lake Tribune.
- 2024. [The power of kindness: fostering a positive culture at Utah State University Uinta Basin](#). Vernal Express.
- 2024. [PittCon Thought Leader: Seth Lyman](#). The Pittcon Podcast.
- 2024. [USU Welcomes Colleen P. Jones as an Associate Research Professor](#). Vernal Express.
- 2024. [Methods of Measuring Atmospheric Mercury Pollution](#). Azo Materials.
- 2024. [Seth Lyman named one of 50 “influential Aggies.”](#) Utah Statesman.
- 2024. [Assistance that never sleeps: Embracing AI in the Uinta Basin](#). Vernal Express.
- 2024. [New research tests AI’s ability to forecast severe weather](#). Heller Weather.
- 2024. [Railroad Commission Approves Toxic Waste Ponds Next to Baptist Camp](#). Inside Climate News.

- 2024. [Bingham Research Center works to improve Utah’s climate](#). Utah Statesman.
- 2024. [Meet The Secretive ‘Mastermind’ Behind Utah's Oil Boom](#). Huffpost.
- 2024. [Zero exceedances of winter ozone this season](#). Basinnow.com.
- 2024. [Winter ozone formation possible next week](#). Basinnow.com.
- 2023. [Elizabeth Cantwell: My vision for a land-grant university in the 21st century](#). Salt Lake Tribune.
- 2023. [The Uinta Basin: Part 2 —Ozone and Collaboration](#). EM.
- 2023. [Research Landscapes](#). USU Today.
- 2023. [Bingham Research Center Hires Senior Air Quality Scientist](#). USU Today.
- 2023. [Wyoming Department of Environmental Quality Air Quality Division Receives National Award](#) (for a model developed by Bingham Center). Wyoming Department of Environmental Quality.

Annual Stakeholder Survey

We conducted an online survey to learn how stakeholders feel about the Bingham Research Center and how they use our research products. We advertised the survey at our exhibitor’s booth and oral presentation at the September 2024 Uintah Basin Energy Summit. We received 22 verified responses.

Survey respondents were asked, “Have you used research products or other output from the USU Bingham Research Center?” Responses included:

- Air quality
- Air quality tracker / alerts
- Uinta Basin air quality monitoring
- Enjoy reading reports and hearing presentations

Survey respondents were asked, “Please provide any suggestions you may have for how the Bingham Center could improve its research products or dissemination of those products.” We didn’t receive any responses to this question.

Survey respondents were asked, “Please provide any suggestions you may have for air quality research or other activities you think the Bingham Research Center should undertake.” We received two substantive responses, both from representatives of the oil and gas industry:

- Collaboration with our operations / LDAR folks
- More involved with industry

Summary of Stakeholder Surveys from 2019 to 2023

We reviewed stakeholder survey responses from 2019 to 2023. Table 1 provides a distillation of our findings. Major themes of the surveys include:

- Increased awareness of BRC
 - Greater promotion of branding
 - More conferences & presentations

- Publish data on websites
- Better dissemination of data
- More involvement of stakeholders
- Improved forecasting of winter ozone
- Increased research
 - Pipelines
 - Pigging
 - Produced water
 - Various emissions
- Educate the public
- Increase grant funding – collaborate with others

Table 1. Summary of Stakeholder Survey Results from 2019-2023.

Suggestions	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
More involvement of stakeholders	X	X	X	X	X
Better dissemination of data	X	X	X	X	X
Greater promotion of branding					X
More conferences, presentations	X	X	X	X	X
Increase awareness of BRC	X				X
Publish data on accessible websites					X
Continued collaboration with others	X	X	X	X	X
Increased research on pipelines/pigs		X	X	X	X
Increased research on VOCs, CO2, NOx			X		X
Improve forecasting of winter ozone	X	X	X	X	X
Educate the public on emissions— Understandable information		X			X
Collaborate with others to secure federal grant funding					X
Research produced water, liquid storage					X

Stakeholder Input Plan for 2025

In past years, we have engaged a Stakeholder Guidance Committee to provide suggestions about our air quality research. The committee has been composed of representatives of the oil and gas industry, regulatory agencies, local and Tribal governments, and environmental groups. Each year, we created a draft research plan, the committee reviewed the plan and provided us with feedback, and we modified the plan based on that feedback. In 2024, we consulted with community and stakeholder engagement specialists at USU’s Transforming Communities Institute about improving this process. We revised the stakeholder engagement process to include the following elements:

1. Engage stakeholders prior to developing research plans: When we shared a detailed research plan with the stakeholder committee, most stakeholders responded that they are happy with the plan. This is the easiest politest response, since we have already created the plan. In the future, we will solicit input from stakeholders about research directions they think we should pursue before we develop or modify our research plans. This will lead to more authentic input and keep the committee from functioning merely as a “rubber stamp.”
2. Hold regular meetings, preferably in person: If engagement with a stakeholder group occurs too infrequently, the stakeholders tend to be less involved or invested in the work for which they are providing guidance. We will contact the stakeholder group at least quarterly. We will also strive to hold some meetings in person. This will be difficult because many decision-makers and stakeholders related to Uinta Basin air quality are based in Salt Lake City, Houston, Denver, or other places. We will discuss this problem with stakeholders and devise a strategy that best meets the needs of stakeholders and the Bingham Center. This may include prioritizing Uinta Basin residents as members of the stakeholder committee. We may consider providing stipends for participants.
3. Ongoing stakeholder input: The Bingham Center’s research projects rarely occur over 12-month periods. Rather than developing annual plans that the stakeholder committee approves, we will give regular updates to the committee about existing projects and seek guidance and prioritization for those projects. This will help the Center focus on actual stakeholder needs.
4. Stakeholder commitment: We will prioritize membership on the stakeholder committee for those individuals who see the value of the Bingham Center’s mission, work and success. Committee members could help promote our work in the community, provide data or site access, collaborate on projects or grant proposals, etc.
5. Community input/engagement: We plan to begin by creating a technical stakeholder committee—a group of individuals with expertise in one or more aspects of the Center’s research. After this committee is organized and functioning, we will form a separate committee of Uinta Basin residents. This will help ensure that we understand the concerns and needs of the community we live and work in and that our research is informed by a broad set of perspectives.

We are recruiting stakeholders to enact this plan now. We expect to have the committee in place and functioning in early 2025. In future annual reports, we will report on the activities of this committee and how our work at the Bingham Center has been guided by them.

Technical Reports

Drone-based Measurement of Emissions from Oil and Gas Sources

Colleen Jones, PhD

Introduction

The oil and gas industry emits methane and other greenhouse gases during extraction, processing, and transportation. Accurately measuring these emissions is critical for regulatory compliance, environmental protection, and climate change mitigation.

Traditional methods for measuring methane emissions often involve ground-based techniques, as described in this report. While effective, these approaches can be time-consuming, limited in spatial coverage, and may not provide real-time data. Additionally, ground-based measurements can miss emissions from hard-to-reach areas, such as remote pipelines and large pieces of equipment or tanks.

Drones equipped with advanced sensors and imaging technology offer a promising solution to overcome the limitations of traditional methods. Here are some key advantages of using drones for methane emissions measurement:

1. **Enhanced Mobility and Access:** Drones can easily reach remote and difficult terrains, allowing for comprehensive monitoring of infrastructure that may be otherwise inaccessible.
2. **High Spatial Resolution:** Drones can cover large areas quickly while providing high-resolution data. This capability enables the detection of localized methane leaks that might be overlooked by stationary monitors.
3. **Real-time Data Collection:** Equipped with sensors, drones can provide real-time data on methane concentrations, facilitating prompt detection and response to leaks.
4. **Cost-effectiveness:** Drones can reduce the labor and time needed for inspections, making them a cost-effective alternative to traditional methods.
5. **Integration with Advanced Technologies:** Drones can be equipped with a variety of sensors, including infrared cameras, laser methane detectors, and optical gas imaging systems, enhancing their ability to detect and quantify methane emissions.

As drone technology continues to evolve, advancements in sensor capabilities, data analytics, and machine learning will enhance the precision and utility of methane emissions monitoring. Collaborations between industry stakeholders, technology providers, and regulatory agencies will be essential to standardize methodologies and maximize the effectiveness of drones in addressing methane emissions.

Progress Report

During this year, Bingham Research Center developed a collaborative relationship with the USU-Eastern Campus Unmanned Aircraft Systems (Drones) - Certificate of Completion program. The collaboration allowed the Center's team to involve students from their program to help build, program, and test a drone-based measurement of methane with a 3D sonic meteorological data station.

The project's initial concepts are built around research by Galfalk, *et al.*[1] The first phase of sensor acquisition and system integration with the drone is almost finished. This included purchasing a Sensit Methane Analyzer, Sparvio 3D sonic meteorological station and SKH3 logger system. The attachment of sensors to the drone is complete. We have initiated several test flights to evaluate the electrical and communication systems to ensure seamless operation between drones and sensors (Figure 1). We are still working on programming the system to streamline the data collection and retrieval.

Figure 1. The USU-Eastern student, who is responsible for the project building, programming, and flying the drone to measure methane emissions from a controlled source.

We are currently working on the continued testing and calibration phase of the project to ensure the accuracy of measurements of methane emissions. This system will include certified source gases (methane, a suite of non-methane organics, NO_x, and CO), a mass flow controller to regulate gas emission rates, and tubing for gas release. We will seek permission from Uintah BasinTech (UBTech) to utilize their non-functional oil and gas equipment for calibration tests,

allowing us to release calibration gas from various points to troubleshoot and refine the drone system.

Figure 2. Output data of methane concentration in ppm from the Sensit Methane Analyzer on a drone test flight completed on September 24, 2024.

As we develop the drone system, we will also create a program to process the data collected during flights. This program will receive a data stream that includes location, meteorological parameters, and chemical data, calculating emission rates based on the mass balance method outlined by Gålfalk, *et al.*[1] Additionally, it will incorporate data on speciated non-methane organics captured by the drone and provide a 3D visualization of the collected data.

Once the drone system, calibration system, and emission calculation software are complete, our focus will shift to collecting emissions measurements from actual oil and gas sources. We will establish collaborations with energy companies to arrange site visits for these measurements. We are still on track for field measurements this fall and to continue networking with the industry to test fly at their locations.

Our systematic approach to developing a reliable and efficient drone-based solution for accurately measuring methane emissions in the oil and gas industry contributes to better environmental monitoring and compliance efforts.

Acknowledgments

The Utah Legislature and Uintah Special Service District 1 funded this research study.

References

1. Gålfalk, M.; Nilsson Påledal, S.; Bastviken, D. Sensitive Drone Mapping of Methane Emissions without the Need for Supplementary Ground-Based Measurements. *ACS Earth and Space Chemistry* **2021**, *5*, 2668-2676, doi:10.1021/acsearthspacechem.1c00106.
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NSF - Collaborative Research: Verification of Atmospheric Mercury Redox Rates

Colleen Jones, PhD

Seth Lyman, PhD

Introduction

This project is a three-year project that addresses the critical gaps in understanding the atmospheric redox chemistry of mercury (Hg), a potent neurotoxin that poses significant risks to both wildlife and human health. Mercury is emitted as elemental Hg (Hg^0) but can be oxidized to its divalent form (Hg^{II}), which is more water-soluble and is rapidly deposited in ecosystems. Current uncertainties regarding the oxidants involved in this transformation and their reaction rates lead to varied predictions of Hg^{II} deposition patterns (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Summary of the global tropospheric mercury budget and main oxidation and reduction pathways in GEOS-Chem for simulations run over 2013–2015. (Adapted from Shah et al., 2021).

Our research is a collaborative effort between Brigham Young University (BYU), the University of Utah (UU), and the University of Nevada, Reno (UNR) with National Science Foundation funding. We will verify the amount of Hg^{II} and its reaction rates by collecting comprehensive datasets in the field to support and change current modeling of atmospheric Hg.

By generating a comprehensive dataset and refining existing measurement techniques, this project aims to reduce uncertainties in mercury redox reaction rates and improve global models of mercury deposition. The outcomes will not only enhance scientific understanding but also have broader implications for air quality predictions and public health policies.

Specific contributions of the proposed project to the body of atmospheric Hg research include:

- A comprehensive dataset of atmospheric Hg and other relevant species (halogens, ozone, NOX, NOY, aerosols, and OH radical) in an area with some of the highest HgII ever measured in North America (Lan, 2012).
- Improvements to and measurements with the only Hg measurement and calibration system that has been shown to quantitatively measure HgII compounds.
- Decrease in the uncertainty of Hg-halogen reaction rates, which are key to Hg0 oxidation, and will help constrain estimates of when, where, and how atmospheric Hg impacts ecosystems.

Year 1 Progress Report

During Year I, our objective was to design, order supplies, and build the mobile field/lab instrumentation and measurement trailer. Students participating with our team this past year have been involved in UNR's Mercury Journal Club with UNR students, and attended a Science for Solutions Conference in Ogden, Utah with researchers and students from all four universities. USU's students have also learned constructing and programming skills while building the mobile field/lab instrument and measurement trailer.

During Year II, we planned to deploy our mobile field/lab trailer at the shore of the Great Salt Lake. However, our original field site at the US Magnesium Plant is no longer feasible. The US Magnesium Plant is uncertain about their return to magnesium production. Currently, they are focusing on extracting other rare earth metals at their site.

Because our ideal field location is no longer available, our other option is a chamber study which would allow us to test our hypothesis. We will still work collaboratively with our team on developing a chamber study at BYU utilizing their chamber and our dual-channel measurement system to verify reactions of Hg0 and HgII, and oxidants such as ozone, methane, HONO, HCHO, Nox, and Br. These compounds facilitate the oxidation of Hg0 and use advanced atmospheric modeling to interpret our findings.

Acknowledgments

All atmospheric mercury research at the Bingham Research Center is funded by the U.S. National Science Foundation.

Public Lands Initiative – Cattail Control Management Strategies for Endangered Fish Habitat on Utah’s Public Lands

Colleen Jones, PhD

Lisa Boyd, PhD Candidate

Introduction

Managing cattail encroachment in the wetlands of Stewart Lake is a costly endeavor, with annual expenses ranging from \$25,000 to \$50,000. Current management practices often lack scientifically validated methodologies and data analysis. Previous research indicates that the breeding success of two endangered fish species at Stewart Lake peaks when cattail cover is around 50%, with the remainder as open water.

This study aims to assess the effectiveness of various cattail treatment methods at the Stewart Lake Wetland Management Area (SLWMA) and provide the Utah Division of Wildlife Resources (UDWR) with a cost-benefit analysis for each management option. We will collaborate with the UDWR, which has secured funding for cattail treatment through Utah’s Watershed Restoration Initiative (UWRI).

The research will evaluate various treatment methods across study plots in the wetlands to identify the most effective approach for controlling cattail encroachment and maintaining it at 50%. We will test the hypothesis that spring treatments, applied before flooding the lake, are as effective as fall treatments conducted after the lake is drained.

The treatment methods under consideration include:

- Herbicide application
- Grazing by goats
- Controlled Burn/Fire

Herbicide will be applied following grazing, using a utility task vehicle (UTV) equipped with a boom, adhering to the manufacturer’s guidelines for wetlands. The Utah Division of Wildlife Resources (UDWR) will provide funding for treatments and materials, managing the purchase, storage, and application of the herbicide.

Utah State University (USU) will assess treatment effectiveness by monitoring cattail canopy cover in designated areas during spring to determine the percentage of cattail growth, and again in summer and fall to measure both cattail and open water cover. We will utilize remote sensing technology, including multispectral satellite imagery for the overall lake area and drone imagery for specific plots. Dr. Colleen Jones from the Bingham Research Center in Vernal, Utah,

is currently leading projects to gather multispectral drone imagery for post-wildfire vegetation and soil stability assessments.

Progress Report

The pretreatment drone survey was completed on July 8, 2024, with Stewart Lake filled with water. Stewart Lake began draining on September 16, 2024. UDWR. At that time, UDWR collected endangered juveniles in fish traps to collect growth indicator measurements and released them back into the adjacent Green River.

During November 6-11, 2024, the initial cattail treatment survey transects and ground truthing plots were set up in partnership with UDWR. The treatment plots were designed to test single treatments as well as combination treatments (Figure 1).

Stewart Lake Cattail Control Management Study

Figure 1. Map of Stewart Lake Cattail Control Management Project’s treatment and ground truthing plots with an aerial RGB base map image collected by USU’s Bingham Research Center UAV team on July 8, 2024.

A second UAV flight with a multispectral camera flew after the treatment plots were established. UDWR will perform the treatments during the fall and spring field seasons. During the winter of 2024/25 the USU graduate student will perform the remote sensing data analysis collected from the two 2024 UAV flights from the multispectral camera. Analysis includes machine learning vegetation classification to assess open water and treatment progress. As well as beginning the cost-benefit analysis of different treatments.

Another cattail treatment survey will happen during the summer of 2025. USU will fly the UAV again after the summer survey to assess the treatments and finalize the cost-benefit analysis to finish the project in December 2025.

Acknowledgment

The project is funded by USU's Public Land Imitative Grant Program.

Winter Ozone Prediction Model

John R. Lawson, PhD

Overview

Episodes of high wintertime ozone in Utah's Uinta Basin can follow a heavy snowstorm when pressure rises and still conditions encourage formation of prolonged cold pools. The snow cover keeps the cold pool stagnant, trapping emissions from the oil and gas industry, leading to sunlight reacting with these emissions to build ozone concentrations. These conditions challenge traditional numerical weather prediction (NWP) models, which must balance computational trade-offs between achieving high resolution (necessary for capturing cold pools and boundary-layer dynamics) and ensemble forecasts (which quantify uncertainty). High-resolution NWP models can simulate small-scale atmospheric interactions essential to winter ozone dynamics, but this computational intensity limits the ability to run ensembles, making uncertainty quantification difficult. This trade-off constrains NWP model utility for capturing the episodic, uncertain nature of cold pools (and hence ozone) in the Basin, making risk-based forecasts difficult to issue.

In response, we have created a lightweight solution that does not require a traditional weather and air-chemistry model. We deploy Clyfar (Welsh for "clever") by implementing a fuzzy inference system (FIS) that synthesises domain knowledge into interpretable rules, creating ozone forecasts without requiring complex parameterisation. Clyfar addresses forecast uncertainty by reframing risk communication through possibility theory, which defines forecast outcomes in terms of plausibility. This framework, which flags high-ozone conditions as possible even under uncertain atmospheric setups, serves risk-averse stakeholders of Ozone Alert by indicating early risks of ozone exceedances. However, implementing possibility theory requires additional development to simplify the mathematics, enhancing accessibility for operational use.

Figure 1: A comparison of traditional yes/no logic (left, a) and fuzzy logic (right, b).

With Clyfar, we improve winter-ozone forecasting by taking information from freely available federal NWP sources that are most related to cold-pool formation (and so high ozone). Fuzzy logic (**Fig. 1**), the core of Clyfar’s FIS, assigns degrees of truth to input conditions—such as “calm wind”—instead of strict binary states, enabling the system to avoid a synthetic sharp transition between, say, “shallow” and “deep” snow that is unknowable (e.g., the amount of snow required to create a persistent cold pool). Clyfar thus captures non-binary conditions linked to ozone formation and translates these into fuzzy rules, creating an inference model that does not require extensive computational resources when using existing NWP data as inputs.

Model configuration and data sources

To inform the prediction system, we obtained observation data from Synoptic Weather. Forecast data is taken from national NWP models. We begin with the NOAA Global Ensemble Forecast System (GEFS) model.

Description of Clyfar configuration

Clyfar’s fuzzy inference system operates on inputs such as snow cover, barometric pressure, and clear-sky radiation. These are categorized into fuzzy states (adjectives such as “deep”) representing observed Basin condition states. The input variables are processed through fuzzy rules informed by known relationships between meteorological conditions and wintertime ozone formation. Clyfar generates forecasts that highlight ranges of plausible ozone outcomes. Possibility distributions over the output categories (*background, moderate, elevated, extreme*) signal varying degrees of ozone risk rather than a binary prediction. This approach enables Clyfar to signal potential ozone episodes with low certainty, enhancing early warning

Figure 2: wind-speed measurements, plotted against ozone measurements (left, a) and defined categories based on data (right, b) capabilities.

Each rule in Clyfar’s system corresponds to expert-identified meteorological thresholds associated with elevated winter ozone. We create the categories based on adjectives of the systems that represent common states, such as wind speed being “calm” or “breezy”: only the two states matter to whether ozone remains in the Basin. We see this in the two panes of **Fig. 2** showing wind speed against ozone concentration, and how we might create categories of “calm” and “breezy” relevant to ozone prediction based on the scatter plot.

We see a divide around 1.5 m/s where speeds stronger than this blow pollution out of the Basin. There is not a sharp number where wind speeds preclude ozone formation. The category shape (“membership value”; curves in **Fig. 3** panels) described how much each value (x-axis) is described by the category’s adjective: we walk through an example below. Rules activate based on conditions like, say, “**calm wind and deep snow leads to elevated ozone**”, named Rule 1 here.

Rule activation demonstration

Figure 3: Example of Rule 1: elevated ozone

The value of each input value is converted to a degree of that category; the activation of the rule (Fig. 3c) is the minimum of the fuzzified input values as described here:

Inference method for Rule 1

1. How calm is the wind? An observed value of 1.6 ms^{-1} gives a degree of “calmness” (Fig. 3a) to 0.77 or “substantially deep” (Table 1)
2. How deep is the snow? For a depth of 9.3 cm this is an activation of 0.38 (“somewhat”) deep (Fig. 3b).
3. We combine the AND rules by finding the minimum across all activations, here $\min(0.77, 0.38) = 0.38$ (cf. Figs. 3c and 5c).
4. Hence we can say elevated ozone is *somewhat possible*.

For generating a forecast, we combine the activation with a maximum of all rules. This is giving the upper bound of likelihood: a pessimistic view or worst-case scenario if the event is undesired as in a high-ozone scenario. This gives users advanced warning of a possibility. This is not as useful as a probability, but there is more transparency about how much confidence is in the forecast. **Figure 4** shows how we can convert the aggregated rule activation to best-case and worst-case scenario outputs. These are created with the 10th and 90th percentile of the possibilities, respectively.

(a) Aggregated activation, representing a possibility distribution π , formed by the union of distributions formed from rules 1 (Fig. 5c) and 2 (Fig. 6b).

(b) Defuzzification through 10th, 50th, and 90th percentiles of the possibilistic area under the curve.

Figure 4: aggregation of rule activations (panel a) formed as the maximum or union of the activations of Rule 1. These are converted to best-, average-, and worst-case scenarios of ozone levels (shown in gray lines, panel b).

Results

Fig. 5 shows a time series of ozone predictions from Clyfar over the winter of 2021–

Figure 6: A winter's time series of Clyfar daily maximum ozone as a representative value for the Basin. Bars and lines are as legend. The three Labeled cases discussed in text as small case studies.

The time series shows observed and forecast sharp (crisp) values, with possibility bars representing the possibility for ozone concentrations categories each day. These evaluations highlighted a mix of forecast strengths and limitations. The time series analysis (Fig XX) contrasts Clyfar's deterministic ozone concentration predictions (blue) against observed values (orange). We find examples (labeled; detailed below) offering a clear view of its performance across typical, poor, and effective forecasts. For instance, Clyfar predicted two high-ozone events within this season, but only one materialized, illustrating both the system's capacity to identify potential high-risk episodes and the need for further calibration. Specific case studies within this season were analyzed to explore different forecast qualities:

14 December 2021 (Background Signal). On this date, Clyfar effectively flagged background ozone levels, assigning a high possibility (~ 0.95) to the "Background" category, with negligible plausibility for elevated concentrations. This demonstrates the system's ability to recognize typical low-ozone conditions.

2 January 2022 (Poor Forecast): In this event, Clyfar assigned a low possibility (~0.3) to elevated ozone levels, which did not fully correspond with observed concentrations. Despite low support in the data, the Clyfar forecast system assigned higher plausibility to extreme values than typical background levels, highlighting the value of preserving a range of possibility bars even in uncertain conditions.

27 February 2022 (Good Forecast): For this episode, Clyfar’s crisp prediction closely aligned with observed sharp increases in ozone, accurately indicating high ozone levels. The possibility bars provided higher plausibility for extreme ozone concentrations, showing accuracy and utility in both a “best-guess” and uncertainty (risk-based) forecast.

Conclusion and Future Work

There are numerous outputs—both tangible and research—from this research that fuel further investigation:

Utility of Possibility Bars in Uncertainty Communication: Including possibility bars alongside sharp values. For example, during the 27 February high ozone event, possibility bars for “High” were substantial, guiding decision-makers toward the high-risk potential without depending solely on the sharp value. These possibility bars allowed stakeholders to interpret a broader risk range, adding a layer of flexibility not available through deterministic values alone. Further work will craft more accessible ways of communicating the idea of possibility forecasts via work with humanities researchers at colleagues and familiar collaborators at the USU Transforming Communities Institute.

Utility for Stakeholders and Decision-Makers. Clyfar forecasts, whether it be deterministic (single value, in units of ppb) or possibility-based outputs (plausibility of ozone categories) provide stakeholders with early indications of possible exceedances, allowing for proactive measures at long lead times (14 days) when even a small signal is highly useful due to risk aversity. This design benefits public health officials, regulatory agencies, and industry operators who can use these early warnings to prepare for potential interventions.

System Limitations and Future Refinements: Clyfar rules are based on the archive of meteorological observations in the Basin. It will produce forecasts implicitly assuming a constant emissions inventory, also. Future developments will refine categories of input variable and the ozone prediction with neural networks, a form of AI that can tune parameters of Clyfar like dials on a radio find the clearest signal. Additional data sources, such as satellite observations and vertical profilers, could support further tending of Clyfar’s rules and variables to strengthen forecast utility.

Software

The codebase for CLYFAR is available free of charge and fully documented at <https://github.com/Bingham-Research-Center/clyfar.git> as part of the Bingham Research Center code repository at <https://github.com/Bingham-Research-Center>. Tickets regarding improvements or bugs can be filed by public users on the GitHub web hosting service under “Issues” to assist our development of CLYFAR .

Scientific Reports

Lawson, J. R., and S. N. Lyman, 2024: A preliminary fuzzy inference system for predicting atmospheric ozone in an intermountain basin. *Air*, **2**, 337–361, <https://doi.org/10.3390/air2030020>.

Lawson, J. R., C. K. Potvin, and K. Nelson, 2024: Decoding the atmosphere: Optimising probabilistic forecasts with information gain. *Meteorology*, **3**, 212–231, <https://doi.org/10.3390/meteorology3020010>.

Lawson, J. R., 2024: Communicating risk with possibility, not probability. *arXiv [stat.AP]*, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2410.21664>.

Presentations and Talks

Training on ozone predictions, UPA Upstream Air Committee Lunch & Learn (also about the website; see Technical Report XX), 20 November 2024.

Lawson, J. R., 2024: “Fuzzy Forecasts of Pollution: Possibility, not Probability”. Applied Math Colloquium series, Dept. of Mathematics and Statistics, Utah State University, Logan, UT.

The Snow Shadow of the Uinta Basin

John Lawson, PhD

Michael Davies

Overview

The group's research has often taken as inherited or assumed wisdom that the Basin experiences a snow (or rain) shadow in the lee of the Wasatch to the West. However, there is to our knowledge no peer-reviewed paper that documents the snow shadow of the Uinta Basin. Further, there is a need to address the following:

- The lack of observations in Duchesne County poses problems for AI models that learn over snow data to better predict air quality. Better knowledge of the snow-shadow pattern can estimate variability based on better observation coverage in Uintah County.
- A documentation of the snow shadow effect from the north (documented in historical geological studies) and south (expected to be weaker due to smoother terrain rise, though wind typically stronger from this direction and hence enhanced wind-flow mechanism)
- Sensitivity of the rain/snow shadow to large-scale wind direction

Background

A rain- or snow-shadow effect occurs when moist air first moves windward up a mountain range, like the Wasatch Mountains in Utah. As the air ascends, it cools and releases moisture, resulting in rain or snow on the windward side (facing the incoming weather). By the time the air crosses over to the leeward side, it has lost much of its moisture, creating a drier region with less precipitation. East of the Wasatch Mountains, the Uinta Basin lies in this shadow, therefore experiencing lower snowfall compared the western side. This variation in snowfall is particularly relevant for studies of winter ozone formation and cold-pool events, especially due to the sparsity of data and lack of documented research into the snow shadow.

Data management/databases

Work on this project has begun accumulation of datasets for analysis:

- Python package synopticPy assists website bringing in observation data
- Pandas will be used for real-time data analysis in python
- parquet is an Adobe format for long-term storage

Future Work

Michael is a first-year undergraduate and balances research with classes. However, we have plans to explore the following in 2025:

- Use of jupyter notebooks to demonstrate analysis such as mapping snowfall
- Mountain meteorology in the Basin as a whole
- Python code structuring and re-use for other projects
- Future application to Clyfar (Technical Report XX)
- Presentation at AMS NOLA 2025 at the student conference was accepted
- Future paper in the MDPI Air journal
- Hydrology variation and impact on the ecosystem
- Review papers on ancient climate (especially in the Uinta Mountains)

Presentations

Lawson, J. R., and Davies, M. J.: The Uinta Basin Snow Shadow: 2022/23 & 2023/24. *8th Science for Solutions Conference*, March 2024, Ogden, Utah. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13937073>

Lawson, J. R., and Davies, M. J., and Seth N. Lyman: Fuzzy winter-ozone predictions. *21st Conference on Mountain Meteorology*, July 2024, American Meteorological Society, Boise, ID

AI Chatbots for Public Science Communication

John R. Lawson, PhD

Overview

This project, documented by the pre-print report in the list at the section end, explores the application of OpenAI's GPT-4 Vision (GPT-4V), experiments done late 2023, in interpreting meteorological charts and communicating weather hazards. Specifically, the work evaluates GPT-4V's competency in delivering understandable and accurate weather forecasts, acknowledging the challenges posed by AI hallucinations—confident but incorrect outputs that could mislead in high-stakes contexts such as severe weather forecasting.

The research's core objectives were to (1) determine whether GPT-4V can interpret meteorological charts accurately and issue its own forecasts (2) evaluate GPT-4V's capacity to communicate these forecasts in audience-specific language, enhancing clarity for diverse stakeholders, and (3) understand the limitations and potential risks in using AI for weather hazard communication.

Preliminary Findings

Initial findings indicate that GPT-4V shows considerable promise in interpreting and describing meteorological charts but also highlights significant challenges. For example:

Accuracy of Interpretation. GPT-4V generally succeeded in interpreting large-scale weather patterns but struggled with finer details, sometimes providing incorrect reasoning in specific outlooks. This limitation suggests the need for human oversight to ensure forecast accuracy.

Language and Cultural Nuances. When translating weather information into Spanish, GPT-4V performed literal translations that lacked the idiomatic precision necessary for effective communication in non-English-speaking contexts. This limitation underscores the need for improved translation mechanisms in AI, especially for nuanced topics like risk communication to specific communities. This is important in a diverse area such as the Basin.

Communication Complexity: While GPT-4V's outputs were coherent, they occasionally presented forecasts in a manner that was too simplistic for expert audiences or too complex for lay audiences, highlighting the challenge of balancing depth and clarity based on the user's knowledge level.

Discussion

The paper emphasizes GPT-4V's utility in complementing human forecasters by rapidly generating preliminary interpretations and visual analyses from meteorological data. However, GPT-4V's **risk of hallucinations** raises concerns, especially when providing high-stakes forecasts that influence decision-making. The need for reliable and precise language is critical in meteorology, as inaccurate or ambiguous forecasts can lead to unnecessary panic or, conversely, underestimation of severe weather threats.

In the context of the *Ozone Alert* system integration of AI chatbots like GPT-4 could streamline the process of generating and disseminating ozone forecasts from Clyfar outputs (see Technical Report XX), which include complex, fuzzy-logic-based predictions of atmospheric ozone concentrations that require simpler language to communicate. Implementing GPT-4V for real-time feedback from users could allow the *Ozone Alert* system to adjust communication dynamically. For example, users could specify their level of understanding or urgency, prompting GPT-4V to adapt its language accordingly. This approach would significantly enhance user engagement and the system's responsiveness to individual needs.

Potential testing and future work

Addressing GPT-4V's translation limitations will be essential for broadening *Ozone Alert*'s reach across non-English-speaking communities. Fine-tuning translations or integrating AI trained specifically for meteorological and air-quality terminology could mitigate current challenges.

Implementing human-in-the-loop processes for high-stakes predictions, such as severe inversion events, to cross-verify chatbot outputs before public release would safeguard against the model's hallucination risks. Additionally, this approach would foster a model for continual improvement by providing corrective feedback to GPT-4V .

In summary, GPT-4V's integration within the *Ozone Alert* program holds significant potential to modernize forecast communication by enhancing the interpretability and accessibility of complex meteorological data. However, the model's current limitations necessitate careful management to prevent miscommunication, particularly in high-risk forecasts like those associated with ozone levels in the Uinta Basin.

Presentations

Lawson, J. R.: "A.I. is an astounding innovation, but can we trust it?". *Science Unwrapped*, November 2024, USU College of Science, Logan, UT

Lawson, J. R., J. E. Trujillo-Falcón, D. M. Schultz, M. L. Flora, K. H. Goebbert, **S. N. Lyman,** C. K. Potvin, and A. J. Stepanek, 2024: Pixels and predictions: Potential of GPT-4V in meteorological imagery analysis and forecast communication. *arXiv [cs.CL]*. (Conditionally accepted for publication in *Artificial Intelligence for Earth Systems*.)

Emissions From an Arrow L-795 Pumpjack Engine: Tests With and Without Modifications for Electronic Fuel Injection

Seth Lyman, PhD

Introduction

This document reports on measurements made in February and August 2024 by scientists at Utah State University's Bingham Research Center of emissions from an Arrow L-795 natural gas-fueled engine that powered an oil pumping unit in the Uinta Basin, Utah. The engine was modified to utilize a prototype electronic fuel injection system, and we measured emissions with the fuel injection system in place and with the engine's original carburetor. The fuel injection system was created by Integrated Power Solutions (57 N Skyline Dr, Roosevelt, Utah). Arrow L-795 and other pumpjack engines in the Uinta Basin are known to operate inefficiently (Lyman et al., 2022b), leading to high emissions of methane and non-methane organics from engine exhaust, and the prototype injection system was intended to improve the engine's operations and decrease pollutant emissions. The Bingham Center agreed to collect the measurements detailed in this report to promote emissions reduction options in the Basin.

1. Methods

Most of the methods used in this work were the same as those employed by Lyman et al. (2022a) and Lyman et al. (2022b), and much of the text in this section is taken from Lyman et al. (2022a).

1.1. Engine Measured

Arrow L-795 engines have two cylinders, are two-stroke, and have a 65-horsepower capacity. The measured engine had a horizontal exhaust stack with a muffler and an internal diameter at the outlet of 102 mm. The stack was elevated about 0.6 m from the ground.

1.2. Field Measurements

1.2.1. Meteorology

During each engine assessment, we measured ambient temperature and relative humidity (New Mountain NM150WX), wind speed and direction (Gill WindSonic), and barometric pressure (Campbell CS100) on a tower extended from the measurement trailer to a height of 6 m. We check these measurements against NIST-traceable standards annually.

1.2.2. Physical and Inorganic Chemical Measurements of Engine Exhaust

We used an Ecom J2KN Pro Industrial analyzer to measure the physical and inorganic chemical properties of the exhaust. The analyzer utilized standard sensors for oxygen (O₂), water vapor, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen monoxide (NO), and nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and an infrared sensor for carbon dioxide (CO₂). The analyzer's inlet line was connected to the exhaust stack between the engine and the muffler with a stainless tube fitting. We collected measurements every 2 sec over 10 min periods in most cases. The Ecom analyzer's probe incorporates a thermocouple to measure exhaust temperature, and the analyzer also measured exhaust pressure. Figure 1 shows a photograph of the sample inlets.

The manufacturer calibrated the Ecom analyzer after the study, and we calibrated chemical measurements one week before the study. Calibration results are available in Section 2.1.2.

Figure 1. Photograph of measurement inlets on the engine exhaust. The leftmost tube connecting to the exhaust is the pitot tube for flow measurement. The middle tube is for the Ecom analyzer, and the rightmost tube is the heated line for organic compound sampling.

1.2.3. Sampling Line for Organic Compounds

We sampled organic compounds via a custom-built, heated sampling line. The tip was a 1.3 cm stainless steel tube with a length of approximately 0.5 m. This tip was connected to the exhaust stack between the engine and the muffler with a stainless tube fitting.

Downstream of the stainless tube was a stainless-steel sintered filter (7 μm pore size) and a PFA Teflon filter pack that held a 47 mm PTFE filter with 5 μm pore size. Installed after the filter pack was a 1 cm PFA Teflon tube of 15 m length. All portions of the inlet line except the stainless-steel tip were heated to 55°C, which was hotter than the dewpoint of the engine exhaust. The sample line led to a generator-powered, on-site trailer and sample gas was flushed through the line at 4 L min⁻¹.

1.2.4. Methane

We used a Los Gatos Research Fast Greenhouse Gas Analyzer with a high-concentration laser to measure methane concentrations in the exhaust gas. The analyzer pulled gas from the sample line in the trailer.

1.2.5. Non-methane Hydrocarbons and Alcohols

Within the research trailer, evacuated sillonite-coated 6 L stainless steel canisters with flow regulated by Alicat mass flow controllers collected gas samples from the sample line. Canisters were filled over 10-minute periods. The line to the canisters and the canisters themselves were unheated (the trailer was heated, but its temperature fluctuated with the ambient temperature and with opening and closing of doors). We analyzed the filled canisters in our laboratory (see Section 1.3.2).

1.2.6. Carbonyls

An independent pump pulled exhaust gas from the sample line through Waters SepPak 2,4 dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH)-coated amorphous silica bead cartridges (350mg) which collected carbonyl compounds. We used two cartridges in series which allowed the second cartridge to capture any breakthrough. The line to the cartridges and the cartridges themselves were heated to 55°C to avoid water condensation. A mass-flow controller regulated flow through the cartridges. We kept cartridges refrigerated to the manufacturer-recommended temperature of <4°C before and after sampling until we completed the analysis. We were cautious to minimize any particulate contaminants on the cartridge and sample container during the handling and the collection of the samples.

1.2.7. Exhaust Flow Measurement

We measured exhaust flow with the Ecom analyzer's pitot tube, flow-measurement probe. The pitot tube was inserted into the exhaust stack between the engine and the muffler with a stainless tube fitting. The tip of the tube was placed in the center of the stack.

1.3. Laboratory Analyses

1.3.1. Dilution of Sample Canisters

After sampling, we diluted fuel gas and exhaust gas sample canisters in the laboratory with ultrapure nitrogen gas to bring the mixing ratios of organic compounds into the range of our gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) system. We pressurized canisters to 3800 mbar and then diluted them with ultrapure nitrogen using an Entech 4600 dynamic diluter. The canisters required multiple stages of dilution for organic compound mixing ratios to be within the range of our GC-MS.

1.3.2. Analysis of Non-methane Hydrocarbons and Alcohols

We analyzed canisters containing diluted fuel gas and exhaust gas samples for a suite of 55 hydrocarbons and three alcohols (see the list of compounds in Table 1-). We used an Entech 7200 pre-concentrator (in cold trap dehydration mode) and 7016D autosampler to concentrate samples and introduce them to a gas chromatograph (GC) system for analysis. The GC system consisted of two Shimadzu GC-2010 GCs, one with a flame ionization detector (FID) and another with a Shimadzu QP2010 Mass Spectrometer (MS). The FID detected C2 and C3 compounds, and the MS detected all other compounds. Details about the method were reported by Lyman et al. (2021) and Lyman et al. (2022b).

**Table 1. List of organic compounds analyzed for this project.
Compound group and analytical method are also shown for each compound.**

Compound	Compound Group	Analytical method
Methane	Methane	LGR analyzer
Ethane	Alkane	GC-MS
Ethylene	Alkene	GC-MS
Propane	Alkane	GC-MS
Propylene	Alkene	GC-MS
Isobutane	Alkane	GC-MS
n-Butane	Alkane	GC-MS
Acetylene	Alkyne	GC-MS
Trans-2-butene	Alkene	GC-MS
1-Butene	Alkene	GC-MS
Cis-2-butene	Alkene	GC-MS
Isopentane	Alkene	GC-MS
N-Pentane	Alkane	GC-MS
Trans-2-pentene	Alkene	GC-MS
1-Pentene	Alkene	GC-MS
Cis-2-pentene	Alkene	GC-MS
2,2-Dimethylbutane	Alkane	GC-MS
Cyclopentane	Alkane	GC-MS

Compound	Compound Group	Analytical method
2,3-Dimethylbutane	Alkane	GC-MS
2-Methylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
3-Methylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
Isoprene	Alkene	GC-MS
1-Hexene	Alkene	GC-MS
n-Hexane	Alkane	GC-MS
Methylcyclopentane	Alkane	GC-MS
2,4-Dimethylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
Benzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
Cyclohexane	Alkane	GC-MS
2-Methylhexane	Alkane	GC-MS
2,3-Dimethylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
3-Methylhexane	Alkane	GC-MS
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
n-Heptane	Alkane	GC-MS
Methylcyclohexane	Alkane	GC-MS
2,3,4-Trimethylpentane	Alkane	GC-MS
Toluene	Aromatic	GC-MS
2-Methylheptane	Alkane	GC-MS
3-Methylheptane	Alkane	GC-MS
n-Octane	Alkane	GC-MS
Ethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
m/p-Xylene	Aromatic	GC-MS
Styrene	Alkene	GC-MS
o-Xylene	Aromatic	GC-MS
n-Nonane	Alkane	GC-MS
Isopropylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
n-Propylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1-Ethyl-3-methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1-Ethyl-4-methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1-Ethyl-2-methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
n-Decane	Alkane	GC-MS
1,2,3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1,3-Diethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
1,4-Diethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC-MS
Methanol	Alcohol	GC-MS
Ethanol	Alcohol	GC-MS

Compound	Compound Group	Analytical method
Isopropanol	Alcohol	GC-MS
Formaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acetaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acrolein	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acetone	Carbonyl	HPLC
Propionaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Crotonaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Butyraldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Methacrolein	Carbonyl	HPLC
2-Butanone	Carbonyl	HPLC
Benzaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Valeraldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Tolualdehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Hexaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC

1.3.3. Analysis of Carbonyls

We eluted and analyzed DNPH cartridges using modifications of the methods of Uchiyama et al. (2009), Anneken et al. (2015), Shimadzu method LAAN-J-LC-E090 (Shimadzu, 2011), and Restek Lit. Cat. # EVSS2393A-UNV (Restek, 2018). These techniques are somewhat different from EPA Method TO-11A (Epa, 1999), which is outdated due to improved instrumentation capabilities. We kept used and unused cartridges refrigerated or on ice, except when installed for sampling. We eluted cartridges within 14 days of sampling and analyzed the eluent within 30 days. To elute DNPH cartridge samples, we flushed cartridges with a 5 mL solution of 75% acetonitrile and 25% dimethyl sulfoxide. We collected the solution into 5 mL volumetric flasks and brought the flasks to a volume of 5ml using 0.5-1 mL of the acetonitrile/dimethyl sulfoxide solution. Finally, we pipetted a 1.6 mL aliquot from the 5 mL flask into two 2 mL autosampler vial for analysis by High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). The second vial was kept as a spare in case of contamination or equipment failure in the lab.

We used a commercial standard mixture (AccuStandard M-1004) of derivatized aldehydes in acetonitrile to develop the calibration curve. We analyzed samples with a Shimadzu Nexera-i LC-2040C 3d Plus HPLC and a Shimadzu Shim-Pack Velox C18 column. We used a mixture of acetonitrile, tetrahydrofuran, and water as the eluent. We calibrated the instrument on each analysis day with a five-point calibration curve. We ran at least one additional calibration standard at the beginning and end of each analysis batch to check for retention time-drift or other errors.

2. Calculation of Emission Rates and Air-fuel Ratio

To calculate the emission rate for each compound, we first multiplied the measured exhaust velocity (m s^{-1}) by the cross-sectional area of the stack (m^2) at its exit to determine the flow rate of the exhausted gas ($\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$). We then multiplied this flow rate by the concentration of each measured compound (g m^3) to ascertain the emission rate of the compound (g s^{-1}). All compounds except carbonyls were measured as mixing ratios (units of parts-per-billion by volume, or ppb). We converted mixing ratios to density units (g m^3) for emission rate calculations at standard conditions of 25°C and one atmosphere. Before calculating emission rates, we converted measured volumetric flow rates to standard flow using these same conditions.

We calculated the air-fuel ratio of each engine using the Brettschneider equation (Brettschneider, 1979) and as the O_2 deficit in exhaust relative to ambient air. For two-stroke pumpjack engines, it is difficult to calculate a correct equivalence ratio from exhaust measurements because of fuel that passes through the engine uncombusted during the combined exhaust— injection step, and it is not clear which method is more accurate. More information about this problem is available here:

<https://online.ucpress.edu/elementa/article/11/1/00064.c/197975/Corrigendum-Low-NOX-and-high-organic-compound>.

2.1. Quality Assurance

2.1.1. Flow Rates

We compared the Ecom pitot tube against a factory-calibrated Pacer DA400 rotating vane anemometer. Because of the bidirectional nature of engine exhaust flow, rotating vane anemometers are not useful for exhaust measurements. We performed the comparison using a 20 cm duct and a blower to generate airflow. The difference between the two instruments was less than 2%.

2.1.2. Inorganics

Table 2 shows calibration recovery results for chemical measurements collected with the Ecom analyzer (i.e., 100% means no difference between the expected and actual results). All results are from the factory calibration except O_2 , which was calibrated at our laboratory. Due to the low calibration recovery for NO_2 , we adjusted NO_2 measurements up by 22% before finalizing the data.

Table 2. Calibration recovery for NO, NO₂, CO, CO₂, and O₂ by the Ecom analyzer.

Gas	Percent recovery
NO	98%
NO ₂	78%
CO	93%
CO ₂	101%
O ₂	100%

2.1.3. Methane

We calibrated the methane analyzer at three points along its measurement range, including one zero point, in the field on the day of measurements. We performed calibrations with four non-zero points prior to the measurement day. We used a custom-built scrubber system to generate methane and carbon dioxide-free air, and we diluted NIST-traceable compressed gas standards with calibrated mass-flow controllers for span calibrations. Calibration zero points were less than 20 ppb. The analyzer has two lasers for methane, one for 0-2000 ppm, and one for concentrations greater than 2000 ppm. Calibration recovery averaged 100% and 99% for the low and high lasers, respectively.

2.1.4. Non-methane Hydrocarbons (NMHC) and Alcohols

Duplicate analyses of canister samples were less than 2% different on average. Blanks contained less than 0.1 ppb of individual organic compounds on average. All results were blank corrected. Recovery of calibration standards averaged 100%, with a maximum and minimum of 120% and 86% for individual compounds.

2.1.5. Carbonyls

Blanks contained less than 0.01 ppb of individual carbonyl compounds on average. All results were blank corrected. Recovery of calibration standards averaged 98%.

3. Results

3.1. Engine Conditions During Sample Collection Periods

The figures shown in this section refer to five different 10-minute sample collection periods. These periods were:

1. Fuel injector test 1: This was a test of the engine with the prototype fuel injection system in place and operating normally.
2. Fuel injector test 2: This was a repeat of fuel injector test 1—all conditions were kept constant to the extent possible.
3. Fuel injector test 3: In this test, the fuel injection system was used to dynamically adjust the amount of fuel to the engine requirements.

4. Carburetor test 1: This was a test of the engine with its original carburetor in place and operating normally.
5. Carburetor test 2: This was a repeat of carburetor test 1—all conditions were kept constant to the extent possible.
6. Upgraded injector test 1: This was a test of the engine with a new, upgraded version of the fuel injection system

All tests were performed in February 2024 except that the upgraded injector test was performed in August 2024.

3.2. Summary of Results

Table 3 contains a summary of results for each of the six collection periods. These results and some of the figures in the next section show that the fuel injector tests had lower emissions than the carburetor tests and that emissions were lowest for the upgraded injector tests.

Table 3. Summary of results for each of the five tests conducted. The meaning of “% of C in organic form” is discussed in the text relating to Figure 3.

	Units	Fuel Injector Test 1	Fuel Injector Test 2	Fuel Injector Test 3	Carbur- etor Test 1	Carbur- etor Test 1	Upgraded Injector Test 1
CO ₂	g/hr	13101	11234	6603	8289	8243	20047
CO	g/hr	49.7	42.8	27.8	2069.3	2186.7	80.8
NO	g/hr	0.2	0.0	0.1	0.6	0.6	0.4
NO ₂	g/hr	4.3	3.4	2.1	3.3	3.3	1.1
Methane	g/hr	1148	975	487	928	956	439
TNMOC	g/hr	540.5	390.0	188.4	347.6	372.9	712.5
Alkanes	g/hr	529.4	382.0	182.4	334.7	359.5	662.3
Alkenes	g/hr	9.9	7.1	5.5	12.3	12.6	34.1
Aromatics	g/hr	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2
Alcohols	g/hr	0.4	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	2.4
Carbonyls	g/hr	0.7	0.5	0.4	0.4	0.4	13.5
O ₂	%	11.2	11.2	9.6	3.3	3.1	7.3
% of C in organic form	%	27	25	22	24	24	14
Exhaust std. flow rate	m ³ /min	2.5	2.2	1.1	1.2	1.2	2.5
Brettschneider air-fuel equivalence ratio	unit-less	1.5	1.6	1.4	0.8	0.8	1.3
O ₂ -based air-fuel equivalence ratio	unit-less	2.2	2.2	1.9	1.2	1.2	1.5
Stack temperature	°C	304	305	347	330	328	415

3.3. Comparison Against Emissions from Other Engines

Figure 2 shows the emission rate of all measured pollutants, except CO₂. Also shown is the average result for six Arrow L795 engines measured by Lyman et al. (2022b). The figure shows that pollutant emission rates were lower for the fuel injector tests than for the carburetor tests and the average emissions from the previous study. The fuel injector tests resulted in much lower CO emissions than tests with the carburetor. Also, in fuel injector tests 1-3, emissions depended strongly on the exhaust gas flow rate. This is expected because emissions are the product of the mixing ratios (i.e., concentrations) of pollutants in the exhaust and the exhaust flow rate. In fuel injector test 3, fuel was dynamically supplied as required by the engine, resulting in a lower exhaust flow rate and the lowest emissions of any test in this study. The upgraded injector test showed relatively low emissions at a much higher exhaust flow rate.

Figure 2. Emissions of all measured pollutants (except carbon dioxide) from the engine in each of the tests in units of grams per hour. TNMOC is a total non-methane organic compounds and is the sum of all the individual organics measured. The top of the bar shows total emissions, and the coloration of the bar shows emissions of individual pollutants or pollutant groups, as indicated in the legend. The leftmost bar is average results for six Arrow L795 engines measured by Lyman et al. (2022b). The whisker on the leftmost bar shows the 95% confidence interval of average total emissions. The black line with black circles shows the exhaust flow rate.

As discussed in detail by Lyman et al. (2022b) (see also their corrigendum) natural gas-burning engines are prone to fuel slip. Fuel slip occurs when fuel passes through the engine uncombusted; it is more likely to occur when the engine is pulling in more air than is necessary for combustion. Also, two-stroke engines are especially prone to fuel slip because they add fuel to the combustion chamber during the exhaust stroke, creating the possibility of some fuel being lost with the exhaust.

We calculated the fuel slip on a molar basis by comparing the mixing ratio in exhaust of carbon atoms in combusted compounds (CO and CO₂) to the mixing ratio of carbon atoms in organic compounds. Since the fuel used by the engines is a mix of organic compounds, the ratio of carbon atoms in organic compounds to total carbon in exhaust indicates the fraction of fuel carbon that was not combusted. Figure 3- shows the mixing ratios of CO, CO₂, methane in units of parts per million (ppm). These three compounds each contain one carbon atom per molecule, so the mixing ratio of carbon is the same as the mixing ratio of the compound. The figure also shows the mixing ratios of different non-methane organic compound groups. These contain more than one carbon atom per molecule, so we multiplied the mixing ratio of each measured compound by the number of carbon atoms it contained to determine the parts per million of carbon (ppmC) of each compound.

Figure 3 also shows the percentage of carbon atoms in exhaust that were in organic molecules. This value is a carbon, atom-based measure of the amount of fuel slip. The amount of fuel slip dropped slightly in fuel injector test 3 but was generally similar in all tests except the upgraded fuel injector test. Those tests were similar to the average of previous measurements of Arrow L795 engines. The upgraded fuel injector test showed a marked reduction in fuel slip.

Figure 3. Mixing ratios (i.e., concentrations) of carbon atoms in individual pollutants or pollutant groups in exhaust, in units of parts per million or parts per million of carbon. The top of the bar shows the total mixing ratio, and the coloration of the bar shows mixing ratios of individual pollutants or pollutant groups, as indicated in the legend. The leftmost bar is average results for six Arrow L795 engines measured by Lyman et al. (2022b). The whisker on the leftmost bar shows the 95% confidence interval of average total emissions. The black line with black circles shows the percentage of carbon atoms in exhaust that were part of organic compounds.

Figure 4 shows emissions of non-methane organic compounds, organized by compound group. Non-methane organic compounds are equivalent to volatile organic compounds, or VOC, except that the regulatory definition of VOC does not include ethane, while non-methane organic compounds do include ethane (it is an alkane). Trends for non-methane organics and VOC are the same. Figure 4 shows that non-methane organics emissions in all the fuel injector tests, except fuel injector test 3 were higher than in tests with the engine’s original carburetor and higher than the average of exhaust measurements from other Arrow L795 engines. Fuel injector test 3, on the other hand, was lower than all other measurements. The high organics emissions in most of the fuel injector tests are due to high exhaust flow rate, since high flow rate leads to higher overall emissions.

As shown in Figure 5, NO_x (i.e., NO + NO₂) emissions in fuel injector tests 1 and 2 were similar to emissions during the carburetor tests and the average of exhaust measurements from other

Arrow L795 engines. Fuel injector test 3 and the upgraded fuel injector test had the lowest emissions of NO_x.

Figure 4. Emissions of groups of non-methane organic compounds from the engine in each of the tests, in units of grams per hour. The top of the bar shows total emissions, and the coloration of the bar shows emissions of each group, as indicated in the legend. The leftmost bar is average results for six Arrow L795 engines measured by Lyman et al. (2022b). The whisker on the leftmost bar shows the 95% confidence interval of average total emissions. The black line with black circles shows the exhaust flow rate.

Figure 5. Emissions of NO and NO₂ from the engine in each of the tests, in units of grams per hour. The top of the bar shows total emissions, and the coloration of the bar shows emissions of each group, as indicated in the legend. The leftmost bar is average results for six Arrow L795 engines measured by Lyman et al. (2022b). The whisker on the leftmost bar shows the 95% confidence interval of average total emissions. The black line with black circles shows the exhaust flow rate.

3.4. Time Series Data

Time series of the five tests are shown in the following figures. Figure 6 shows fuel injector tests 1 and 2, Figure 7 shows fuel injector test 3, and Figure 8 shows carburetor tests 1 and 2. The cyclical nature of exhaust properties and composition in the figures coincides with strokes of the pumping unit.

Figure 9 shows only two minutes of a time series so the cycle can be better visualized. It shows that the cycle of exhaust O₂ levels is opposite to the cycle for NO_x and CO₂, and CO, but is in sync with the cycle for hydrocarbons. These cycles are on the same time scale as exhaust temperature, but with a lag. Lyman et al. (2022b) postulated that, as the engine load increases when pulling the pumping unit up, more fuel is used, which increases the exhaust temperature (and the unmeasured engine temperature) and decreases O₂ and uncombusted fuel in the exhaust. Higher engine temperatures lead to more NO_x production, and increased combustion leads to more CO₂ and CO production. Then, as the pumping unit descends and the engine load decreases, the engine consumes less fuel, the exhaust temperature declines, and all these trends are reversed.

At higher combustion temperatures, fuel slip can be expected to decrease, and NO_x emissions can be expected to increase. Exhaust temperatures were similar for all five engine tests, which probably explains why fuel slip and NO_x emissions were also similar for all tests.

Figure 6. Time series of measurements collected during fuel injection tests 1 and 2. All measurements shown were collected at 2-second intervals, except methane, which was collected at 20-second intervals.

Figure 7. Time series of measurements collected during fuel injection test 3. All measurements shown were collected at 2-second intervals, except methane, which was collected at 20-second intervals.

Figure 8. Time series of measurements collected during carburetor tests 1 and 2. All measurements shown were collected at 2-second intervals, except methane, which was collected at 20-second intervals.

Figure 9. Two minutes of the time series for fuel injector test 3. All measurements shown were collected at 2-second intervals. Hydrocarbons are shown rather than methane. This hydrocarbon measurement was collected by an infrared sensor on the Ecom analyzer. Other measurements of methane and non-methane organics were collected as described in methods. The Ecom hydrocarbon measurement has been found to be unquantitative, but it provides an accurate measure of emission trends across time. It is shown here because it is available at 2-second intervals, while other organics measurements collected for this study are only available at longer

intervals.

Figure 10. Time series of measurements collected while the engine was being adjusted to decrease O₂ intake. All measurements shown were collected at 2-second intervals except methane, which was collected at 20-second intervals.

Figure 10 shows a time series for a period when the fuel injection system was used to dynamically change air intake by the engine, as well as other controllable engine parameters, to increase combustion temperature and decrease fuel slip. The figure shows the percentage of carbon atoms in the exhaust that were contained within organic compounds, which is a measure of fuel slip. Measurements of non-methane organics were not available during this period, so the percentage of carbon in organic compounds was calculated using only methane data and is underestimated. Nonetheless, the figure shows that modification of engine parameters can lead to changes in fuel slip. Indeed, the figures show that fuel slip varied by more than two times.

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Understanding the Key Components of Winter Ozone Formation & the Influence of Chemical Mechanisms

Seth Lyman, PhD

Introduction

The Uinta Basin is located in the northeastern corner of Utah which is renowned for its natural beauty and rich energy resources. In recent years, it has faced a unique environmental challenge of elevated tropospheric ozone during the winter months (1). This phenomenon is primarily attributed to a combination of thermal inversion, snow cover, and emission of pollutants from the oil and gas industry. Uinta Basin is surrounded by high mountains, creating a bowl-shaped terrain, which is ideal for creating strong thermal inversions. During thermal inversions, colder air is trapped beneath warmer air, which traps the pollutant near ground level, leading to elevated ozone concentrations. Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and nitrogen oxides (NO_x) released from the oil and gas production pads interact with sunlight and undergo photochemical reactions to produce ozone (2). Among VOCs, Carbonyl compounds are found to be important precursors in winter ozone formation, but their chemistry during winter ozone episodes has not been thoroughly investigated. Box models can be useful in air quality studies because they simplify the atmosphere into a single box. It allows modification and adjustments of input parameters like precursor emission rates which helps in detailed analysis of atmospheric chemistry (3).

Method

In this study, (a) we used the FOAM Box Model along with four different chemical mechanisms to identify the specific carbonyl species that act as important precursors to winter ozone formation and determine how they form; (b) we determined the modeled emission factors for carbonyl compounds, (c) we assessed the ozone formation potential of different carbonyl compounds, and (d) analyzed the sensitivity of various primarily emitted organic species (alkane, alkene, alkyne, alcohols and aromatics) to carbonyl compounds to provide information about how different hydrocarbon species regulate the production of ozone and carbonyl compounds. As researchers, we utilized a subset of the Master Chemical Mechanism version 3.3.1 (MCMv331) (4), which consists of 3423 species and 10309 reactions as the base chemical mechanism with the FOAM Box model. Then we compared MCMv331 output with lumped chemical mechanisms such as Regional Atmospheric Chemistry Mechanism (RACM2) (5), Statewide Air Pollution Research Center Chemical Mechanism version 07 (SAPRC07) (6), and

Carbon Bond Chemical Mechanism version 6 (CB6) (7). We adjusted the Emission factors until modeled carbonyl concentrations matched measured values. Final emission factors were zero or nearly zero, which indicates carbonyl compounds were mostly secondary pollutants, created in the atmosphere from photochemistry. The simulation period was between February 24-27, 2019, which was suitable for studying high winter ozone events. The average hourly meteorological data from each 4-day model period was used as input for each modeled day.

Results

Throughout the simulation period, the maximum measured ozone concentration was 102 parts per billion (ppb). Among the different chemical mechanisms, the RACM2 produced the closest estimate of the observed value, predicting an ozone level of 100 ppb. The MCMv3.3.1 and SAPRC07 provided similar estimates, ranging between 108 and 111 ppb, thus slightly overestimating the measured level. On the other hand, the CB6 mechanism considerably overestimated ozone, predicting a concentration of 123 ppb.

Figure 1 represents the contribution of carbonyls in winter ozone formation in different chemical mechanisms. Based on MCMv3.3.1, RACM2, and SAPRC07 mechanisms, we identified formaldehyde as the most impactful carbonyl compound contributing to change in ozone production rate, with acetaldehyde being the second most important. On the other hand, the CB6 mechanism identified ketones as the major contributor to ozone production. CB6 mechanism is based on carbon-carbon bonds rather than actual chemical species which considers most of the carbonyl as ketones causing ketones as the highest contributor. Furthermore, in both the MCMv3.3.1 and SAPRC07 mechanisms, benzaldehyde exhibited a negative impact on ozone production, indicating its inhibitory role within these models.

Figure 1: Impact of Different Carbonyl Compounds on Ozone Production.

We identified Carbonyls to be secondarily produced through the oxidation of primarily emitted organic compounds with O_2 in the atmosphere. Figure 2 represents the sensitivity of alkane, alkene, alkyne, alcohol, and aromatics to the formaldehyde and acetaldehyde in different chemical mechanisms. The MCMv3.3.1, SAPRC07, and RACM2 mechanisms showed similar chemistry in the formation of formaldehyde, where formaldehyde showed the highest sensitivity to alkene & alkynes followed by alkane as the second highest. On the other hand, in the CB6 mechanism, the sensitivity of alkene and alkyne was significantly higher than in other mechanisms, in addition, alkane was indicated as a negative contributor. In terms of acetaldehyde, we found alkanes to be the most sensitive species in all chemical mechanisms. Other carbonyls such as methacrolein, benzaldehyde & methyl ethyl ketone showed the highest sensitivity to alkanes based on MCMv331. It is nearly the same for SAPRC07 and RACM2.

Figure 2: Percent Changes in Average Carbonyl Concentration.

We also determined the direct impact of primarily emitted organics on the winter ozone formation. Figure 3 shows the Sensitivity of Primary Emitted Organics to winter Ozone formation. In the MCMv3.3.1 and SAPRC07 mechanisms, alkanes were the primary contributors to the reaction, with aromatics as the secondary contributors. The RACM2 mechanism indicated a nearly equal contribution from both alkanes and aromatics. In contrast, the CB6 mechanism highlighted alkanes as the main contributors, with alkenes and alkynes following in significance.

Figure 3: Sensitivity of Primary Emitted Organics to Ozone

Conclusion

The RACM2 mechanism, when applied with the FOAM Box model, produced an ozone level prediction closest to the measured value. Formaldehyde emerged as the most significant carbonyl compound for ozone production, with acetaldehyde as the second most impactful. According to the MCMv3.3.1 and SAPRC07 mechanisms, alkanes were the primary contributors to ozone formation, with aromatics playing a secondary role. From the overall comparison of chemical mechanisms, we can conclude that CB6 could be useful as a lumped chemical mechanism to use with different air quality models in estimating different pollutants in the atmosphere. However, it might not be the best option for understanding the underlying chemistry.

Next Steps

This project is part of a larger ongoing study to improve methods for modeling wintertime ozone formation. The work discussed here will be published in a peer-reviewed journal in early 2025, and a follow-on project that will involve testing different chemical mechanisms in the CMAQ 3D photochemical model is underway.

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Air Quality Trends

Seth Lyman, PhD

Introduction

The purpose of this section is to track changes in Uinta Basin air quality, including changes in pollutant levels in the atmosphere and the reasons for those changes. We seek to answer:

1. Are levels of ozone and its precursors changing over time?
2. What are the causes of any changes that occur?

In general, temporal trends in ozone and its precursors, if they exist, can be expected to be caused by changes in meteorology or changes in pollutant emissions. In this section, we use statistical methods to attempt to separate the two.

Ozone

Figure 1 shows a time series of ozone concentrations at several sites in the Uinta Basin from July 2009 (when continuous measurements began) through August 2024. As the figure shows, the 4th highest 8-hr average ozone concentration was greater than the EPA standard at at least one location during eight of the 15 winters for which measurement data are available (53%). Ozone statistics from the sites shown in Figure 1 are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. Time series of daily maximum 8-hr average ozone concentration at five sites in the Uinta Basin from July 2009 through August 2024. The red dashed line shows 70 ppb, the EPA standard for ozone.

Table 1. Ozone summary statistics for five sites in the Uinta Basin over 15 calendar years.
All values were calculated from daily maximum 8-hr average concentrations. For 2024, only data through August are shown.

Year	Site	Mean	Median	Max	Min	4 th High Daily Max	Exceedance Days (>70 ppb)
2009 (July-Dec)	Ouray	47	47	101	23	67	1
	Vernal	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Roosevelt	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Whiterocks	--	--	--	--	--	--
2010	Ouray	56	54	123	20	117	45
	Vernal	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Roosevelt	--	--	--	--	--	--
	Whiterocks	--	--	--	--	--	--
2011	Ouray	54	52	138	18	119	28
	Vernal	55	55	95	33	84	12
	Roosevelt	56	54	116	30	103	21
	Whiterocks	--	--	--	--	--	--
2012	Ouray	49	50	76	18	67	1
	Vernal	45	46	68	14	64	0
	Roosevelt	50	51	70	14	67	0
	Whiterocks	--	--	--	--	--	--
2013	Ouray	58	54	141	24	133	52
	Vernal	53	52	114	20	102	32
	Roosevelt	56	54	110	18	104	35
	Whiterocks	--	--	--	--	--	--
2014	Ouray	48	49	91	17	79	8
	Vernal	44	46	64	12	62	0
	Roosevelt	51	51	63	29	62	0
	Whiterocks	47	48	67	24	64	0
2015	Ouray	46	47	71	21	68	2
	Vernal	43	43	67	10	64	0
	Roosevelt	44	44	66	24	60	0
	Whiterocks	47	47	73	25	68	2
2016	Ouray	49	48	120	20	96	11
	Vernal	47	46	78	20	73	5
	Roosevelt	47	47	96	20	81	5
	Whiterocks	48	48	86	29	81	7
2017	Ouray	50	50	111	20	103	11
	Vernal	48	49	69	25	68	0
	Roosevelt	48	48	86	24	78	8
	Whiterocks	46	46	76	27	66	1
2018	Ouray	48	48	72	18	67	1
	Vernal	48	50	81	20	69	2
	Roosevelt	49	49	79	18	71	8

Year	Site	Mean	Median	Max	Min	4 th High Daily Max	Exceedance Days (>70 ppb)
2019	Whiterocks	47	46	71	22	69	1
	Ouray	50	51	110	21	98	16
	Vernal	47	48	76	16	65	1
	Roosevelt	50	51	96	19	87	10
2020	Whiterocks	48	49	74	23	67	3
	Ouray	49	48	74	26	65	1
	Vernal	42	41	67	14	63	0
	Roosevelt	46	47	71	24	63	1
2021	Whiterocks	47	47	73	28	65	1
	Ouray	50	50	73	21	72	5
	Vernal	47	47	72	23	68	3
	Roosevelt	48	48	77	20	72	4
2022	Whiterocks	49	48	75	25	68	1
	Ouray	46	46	68	23	64	0
	Vernal	46	46	66	20	63	0
	Roosevelt	47	48	71	21	66	1
2023	Whiterocks	47	47	63	27	62	0
	Ouray	49	49	102	14	91	27
	Vernal	47	50	101	14	82	12
	Roosevelt	49	50	112	11	93	23
2024 (Jan-Aug)	Whiterocks	50	51	105	18	88	13
	Ouray	42	43	66	18	57	0
	Vernal	46	48	74	15	68	3
	Roosevelt	48	49	78	17	69	2
	Whiterocks	49	50	76	24	70	3

Utah DAQ also measured ozone in Vernal during 2006 and 2007, but those data are not publicly available and are not included here. No wintertime exceedances of the ozone standard were measured in Vernal during that period.

The three-year average of annual fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr averages for a given site (using calendar years) is referred to as a design value. The design value is the value EPA uses to determine whether an airshed is in attainment of the 70 ppb ozone standard (design values of 71 and above are out of attainment). EPA used the 2014-16 period in their 2018 decision to designate the Uinta Basin as a nonattainment area for ozone. Table 2 shows the ozone design value for the past several three-year periods for the same monitoring stations shown in Figure 1. The design value for 2022-24 shown in Table 2 only includes data through August 2024. Note that these are not official design values. Regulatory agencies may exclude some data or consider other criteria in the process of determining official design values.

Table 2. Average of the fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone during three consecutive calendar years for several monitoring stations in the Uinta Basin (a.k.a. ozone design values). Only 2024 data collected through August are used. Values in exceedance of the EPA standard are in bold font. Values shown may include summertime ozone events that could be excluded from regulatory consideration.

Station	Ouray	Vernal	Roosevelt	Whiterocks
2013-15	93	76	75	66
2014-16	81	66	67	71
2015-17	89	68	73	71
2016-18	88	70	76	72
2017-19	89	67	78	67
2018-20	76	65	73	67
2019-21	78	65	74	66
2020-22	67	64	67	65
2021-23	75	71	77	72
2022-24	70	71	76	73

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the number of ozone exceedances and the annual fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone, respectively, for each entire calendar year at the same monitoring stations shown in the previous tables and figures. These figures show that air quality is extremely variable from year to year and across measurement stations in the Uinta Basin. For example, Ouray experienced more than 40 exceedance days in 2010 and 2013 but had only one in 2012, 2018, and 2020, and only two in 2015. Some exceedances shown in Figure 2 occurred during summer, not winter, and the summertime exceedances were likely due to intrusions of ozone-rich stratospheric air or wildfires.

Figure 3 shows that the fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone at the five sites is always about 60 ppb or higher. The natural summertime background ozone level in the intermountain western United States is 60 to 65 ppb (Parrish et al., 2022). During years with low wintertime ozone (2012, 2015, 2018, 2020, 2022, and 2024), the highest ozone is observed during summer and is usually in the range of 60-65 ppb. Ozone is also spatially variable. Figure 3 shows that Ouray and Roosevelt tend to have higher ozone than Vernal.

Figure 2. Number of annual ozone exceedances at five sites from 2010 through August 2024. The grey bars indicate years with little snow cover.

Figure 3. Annual fourth-highest 8-hr average daily maximum ozone at five sites from 2010 through August 2024. The red-dashed line indicates 70 ppb, the current EPA standard for ozone. The grey bars indicate years with little snow cover.

Particulate Matter

Figure 4 shows a time series of all PM_{2.5} measurements that have ever been collected in the Uinta Basin. Exceedances of the EPA PM_{2.5} standard sometimes occur during winter but are more common during summer months. These summertime spikes in PM_{2.5} concentrations are typically caused by wildfire smoke.

Figure 4. Time series of daily 24-hr average $PM_{2.5}$ concentrations at nine sites in the Uinta Basin, October 2009-March 2024. The red-dashed line shows $35 \mu g m^{-3}$, the EPA standard for $PM_{2.5}$.

Trends in the Capacity of Winter Inversion Episodes to Produce Ozone

Ozone Exceedance Days

The number of exceedances of the EPA ozone standard show a decreasing trend (Mansfield and Lyman, 2021) from 2010 through 2022. Figure 2 shows all exceedance days by calendar year, including those that occur during summer. The decreasing trend is clearer in Figure 5, which shows only wintertime exceedances by winter season. Mansfield and Lyman (2021) showed that NO_x emissions also decreased over the same period and Lin et al. (2021) showed that methane emissions also decreased over the same period. Mansfield and Lyman (2021) attributed the decline in ozone and its precursors to (1) a decline in energy production (which was driven mostly by a decline in natural gas production) and (2) regulatory and voluntary action by the oil and gas industry to reduce emissions.

Figure 5. Number of ozone exceedance days per winter season and total energy production per year in units of barrels of oil equivalent (i.e., sum of oil production and gas production scaled to equivalent amount of energy. The number of exceedance days at the monitoring station in the Basin with the maximum number in any given winter season is shown. Winters with at least 15 days with snow depth greater than 5 cm are shown in red and other years are shown in grey.

Figure 5 shows that the declining trend in winter ozone reversed sharply in 2023 when deep snow cover and many strong inversions allowed for many exceedance days. The figure shows that oil and gas production have also increased, and increased emissions most likely also contributed to increased ozone in 2023.

Dependence on Meteorological Conditions

As Figure 5 shows, significant local production of wintertime ozone has never occurred and cannot occur without significant snow cover across the Uinta Basin (Oltmans et al., 2014). Indeed, winter ozone levels are positively correlated with snow depth ($r^2 = 0.50$ for the Horsepool site). The number of winter exceedance days is more strongly correlated with the season-average inversion strength; however, since snow cover sometimes exists in stormy or windy conditions that don't allow for strong winter inversion episodes, strong winter inversion episodes seldom occur without snow cover, and winter ozone needs inversions and snow to form (Mansfield, 2018). (Figure 6)

Figure 6 plots the number of ozone exceedance days per season against the pseudo-lapse rate. The lapse rate is the inverse of the change in temperature with altitude. The lower the lapse rate, the stronger the inversion. Typically, lapse rates are measured by releasing temperature sensors attached to helium balloons, but these measurements are expensive and have rarely been performed in the Uinta Basin. As an alternative, Mansfield (2018) used temperature measurements from surface stations at different elevations to approximate the lapse rate (a "pseudo" lapse rate). We follow Mansfield's method of determining pseudo-lapse rates in this section.

Figure 6. Number of ozone exceedance days per winter season versus seasonal average pseudo-lapse rate. Pseudo-lapse rate is a measure of inversion strength (more negative value indicates stronger inversion) and is discussed at length by Mansfield (2018). The orange dashed line is a linear regression that only includes seasonal average pseudo-lapse rates less than 2 K km⁻¹.

Figure 7 shows the difference between actual ozone exceedance days per winter season and the number of exceedance days expected from the relationship shown in Figure 6-. The figure shows an apparent decreasing trend over time, meaning that fewer exceedance days than expected have occurred in recent years. This could indicate that, for similar seasonal conditions, the capacity of the Uinta Basin atmosphere to produce ozone has decreased.

Figure 7. The number of excess ozone exceedance days per winter season relative to the amount expected from the relationship is shown in Figure 6-. Only years with seasonal average pseudo-lapse rates less than 2 K km⁻¹ are shown.

Trends in Ozone Precursors

Mansfield and Lyman (2021) used a linear regression of daily maximum 8-hr average ozone against daily pseudo-lapse rate to “correct” ozone for inversion strength. Mansfield and Lyman

(2021) found that the daily pseudo-lapse rate and the daily maximum 8-hr average ozone for most winter seasons were correlated. They used the linear regression for each season to calculate the daily maximum 8-hr average ozone value that would be expected for a pseudo-lapse rate of -15 K km^{-1} in that season, and they called this metric $\langle [\text{O}_3] \rangle_{-15}$. Since the $\langle [\text{O}_3] \rangle_{-15}$ normalizes for the influence of inversion strength on ozone production, they assumed that year-to-year differences in $\langle [\text{O}_3] \rangle_{-15}$ were due to differences in ozone-forming emissions, not differences in meteorology. Mansfield and Lyman showed that $\langle [\text{O}_3] \rangle_{-15}$ declined from 2010 to 2020, and they attributed this decline to declines in NO_x and organic compound emissions.

We applied the method of Mansfield and Lyman (2021) to methane, NO_x , and non-methane hydrocarbon emissions to separate emission trends from meteorological variability. We calculated linear regressions of the pseudo-lapse rate versus daily average methane, NO_y (as a proxy for NO_x , since NO_y is the sum of NO_x and its photochemical degradation products) and total non-methane hydrocarbons measured at Horsepool and Roosevelt. We calculated separate regression equations for each site for each year for which data were available. We omitted days with relatively uncertain pseudo-lapse rates ($r^2 < 0.3$ for the relationship between temperature and elevation).

The pseudo-lapse rate was predictive of the majority of the variability in methane, NO_y , and non-methane hydrocarbons (r^2 or 0.61 ± 0.21 , 0.63 ± 0.21 , and 0.56 ± 0.22 , respectively: average \pm standard deviation). We determined residuals by subtracting predicted daily concentrations from measured concentrations. Daily average concentrations of methane, NO_y , and non-methane organics were significantly correlated with temperature, wind speed, the number of consecutive inversion days and the number of days since the winter solstice. The residuals, however, were not significantly correlated with any of these variables, which indicates that regression against the pseudo-lapse rate was adequate to account for the influence of these other variables on daily average concentrations.

Following Mansfield and Lyman (2021), we applied site-and-year-specific regression equations to ascertain the daily average concentrations that would be expected in each winter season at a pseudo-lapse rate of -15 K km^{-1} . The results are shown in Figure 1-8 through Figure 1-10. Since this method considers the propensity of methane, NO_y and non-methane hydrocarbon concentrations to increase under inversion conditions, and since no other significant meteorological correlations existed after inversion strength was taken into account, we attribute the temporal trends in the figures to changes in emissions. We acknowledge that the trends shown in the figures may be local and that more work is needed to verify whether these trends hold true for the Uinta Basin as a whole.

Figure 8. Daily average NO_y (a proxy for NO_x) at a pseudo-lapse rate of -15 K km⁻¹ as predicted from year- and site-specific linear regressions of NO_y against the pseudo-lapse rate. Whiskers show the combined uncertainty of the pseudo-lapse rate calculation and the NO_y measurement.

Figure 9. Daily average methane at a pseudo-lapse rate of -15 K km⁻¹, as predicted from year- and site-specific linear regressions of methane against the pseudo-lapse rate. Whiskers show the combined uncertainty of the pseudo-lapse rate calculation and the methane measurement.

Figure 10. Daily average total non-methane hydrocarbons at a pseudo-lapse rate of -15 K km^{-1} , as predicted from year- and site-specific linear regressions of non-methane hydrocarbons against the pseudo-lapse rate. Whiskers show the combined uncertainty of the pseudo-lapse rate calculation and the non-methane hydrocarbons measurement.

The results for Horsepool are similar to the findings of Mansfield and Lyman (2021) and Lin et al. (2021), which all show that emissions of methane, NO_x , and non-methane hydrocarbons have declined since 2013. Figures 8 through 10 do not show a meaningful trend in any of the compounds at Horsepool after 2017, even though energy production and oil and gas activity changed considerably over that time. No clear trend exists for methane and non-methane hydrocarbons at Roosevelt, perhaps because of the site’s shorter hydrocarbon measurement record. The NO_y trend at Roosevelt is dominated by a strong upswing in winter 2023. Several large flares at oil wells were active near the Roosevelt site during winter 2023, and these could be the cause of high NO_y in 2023.

Acknowledgments

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Winter 2023-24 Air Quality and Meteorology

Seth Lyman, PhD

This section reports on air quality conditions that occurred during winter 2023-24.

Methods

Quality assurance results for the methods described here are available in the section reporting team performance for 2024.

Ozone

During winter 2023-24, eleven monitoring stations measured ozone operated in the Uinta Basin. Table 1- contains a list of all monitoring stations, including locations, elevations, and operators. We obtained data for stations operated by organizations other than USU from the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)'s AQS database (<https://aqg.epa.gov/api>) and airnowtech.org. We utilized an Ecotech Model 9810 ozone analyzer at the Horsepool site and 2B Technology Model 205 ozone monitors at other stations operated by USU. We performed calibration checks at all USU stations at least every other week using NIST-traceable ozone standards. Calibration checks passed if monitors reported in the range of ± 5 ppb when exposed to 0 ppb ozone and if monitors were within $\pm 7\%$ deviation from expected values when exposed to higher concentrations of ozone. We only included data bracketed by successful calibration checks in the final dataset.

Table 1. Air quality monitoring stations operating during winter 2023-24. All stations measured ozone and basic meteorological parameters. Stations that measured organic compounds, NO_x, and/or PM_{2.5} are indicated. NO_x* signifies NO₂ measured with a photolytic NO₂ (rather than molybdenum) converter. NPS is the National Park Service. UDAQ is the Utah Division of Air Quality. BLM is the Bureau of Land Management. AQS is the EPA AQS air quality database (<https://aqs.epa.gov/api>).

	Operator	Latitude	Longitude	Elev. (m)	Organics	NO _x , PM _{2.5}	Data Source
Seven Sisters	USU	39.981	-109.345	1618	N/A	N/A	USU
Castle Peak	USU	40.051	-110.020	1605	Yes	NO _x *	USU
Dinosaur N.M.	NPS	40.437	-109.305	1463	N/A	N/A	AQS
Red Wash	Ute Tribe	40.204	-109.352	1689	N/A	NO _x	AQS
Vernal	UDAQ	40.453	-109.510	1606	N/A	NO _x , PM _{2.5}	AQS
Whiterocks	Ute Tribe	40.484	-109.906	1893	N/A	NO _x	AQS
Ouray	Ute Tribe	40.055	-109.688	1464	N/A	NO _x	AQS
Roosevelt	DAQ/USU	40.294	-110.009	1587	Yes	NO _x *, PM _{2.5}	AQS/USU
Myton	Ute Tribe	40.217	-110.182	1610	N/A	NO _x	AQS
Horsepool	USU	40.144	-109.467	1569	Yes	NO _x *, PM _{2.5}	USU
Rangely	NPS/BLM	40.087	-108.762	1648	N/A	NO _x , PM _{2.5}	AQS

Reactive Nitrogen

We measured NO, true NO₂ (via a photolytic converter), and NO_y at Roosevelt with a Teledyne-API NO_x analyzer. We measured NO, true NO₂, and NO_y with a Thermo 42i with a photolytic converter at Horsepool, and we measured NO and true NO₂ with a Thermo 42i with a photolytic converter at Castle Peak. All three photolytic converters were manufactured by Air Quality Design, Inc. NO_x is the sum of NO and NO₂. NO_y is the sum of NO_x and other reactive nitrogen compounds in the gas and fine particulate phases. We calibrated the systems weekly with NO standards and for NO₂ and NO_y via gas-phase titration using a dilution calibrator. Once during the season, we calibrated NO_y instrumentation with nitric acid and isopropyl nitrate permeation tubes. All sites operated by other organizations measured NO and NO₂ via a molybdenum converter-based system, a method known to bias NO₂ and NO_x results high due to NO_y interference (Jung et al., 2017). Methane and Total Non-methane Hydrocarbons

We measured methane and total non-methane hydrocarbons at Horsepool and Roosevelt with a Chromatotec ChromaTHC and a Thermo 55i, respectively. We calibrated these systems every week with certified gas standards (containing methane and propane) and a dilution calibrator.

Speciated Non-methane Hydrocarbons and Alcohols

To measure speciated non-methane hydrocarbons and alcohols, we collected whole-air samples with silonite-coated 6 L stainless steel canisters at Horsepool, Roosevelt, and Castle Peak. We collected at most one can per day via an automated sampling manifold (we filled some cans from 0:30 to 3:30 local standard time and the others from 12:30 to 15:30). We used

silonite-coated, critical orifice-based flow regulators to regulate flow into the canisters, and we controlled sample collection with a nickel-plated brass manifold with inert solenoid valves (Clippard part number O-ET-2M-12). Tubing and fittings were all either PFA Teflon or stainless steel. A PTFE filter upstream of the sample line filtered particles (5 µm pore size).

We analyzed the canisters for 54 hydrocarbons, methanol, ethanol, and isopropanol using a method similar to guidance provided by EPA for Photochemical Assessment Monitoring Stations (EPA, 1998). We used cold trap dehydration (Wang and Austin, 2006) with an Entech 7200 preconcentrator and a 7016D autosampler to preconcentrate samples. We analyzed samples with two Shimadzu GC-2010 gas chromatographs (GCs), a flame ionization detector (for C2 and C3 NMHC), and a mass spectrometer (for all other compounds). We used a Restek rtx1-ms column (all compounds; 60 m, 0.32 mm ID), a Restek Alumina BOND/Na₂SO₄ column (C2 and C3 NMHC; 50 m, 0.32 mm ID), and another Restek rtx1-ms column (all other compounds; 30 m, 0.25 mm ID) to separate compounds in the GCs.

We used 5-point curves to calibrate the flame ionization detector and mass spectrometer at least monthly. We analyzed a duplicate sample, at least one blank, and at least one calibration check during each batch. We accepted data if calibration curves had r^2 values greater than 0.99, if all values for blanks were less than 1 ppb, if duplicate values for each compound averaged within 10% of each other, and if calibration checks for each compound were within 20% of expected values. We used blank values to correct sample results.

More information about our canister analysis protocols and results is available in Lyman et al. (2021) and Lyman et al. (2018). Table 1-2 lists the organic compounds measured.

Table 2. List of organic compounds measured, the compound group for each, and the analytical method used.

Compound	Group	Analytical method
Ethane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Ethylene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
Propane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Propylene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
Isobutane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
n-Butane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Acetylene	Alkyne	GC/GC/MS
Trans-2-butene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
1-Butene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
Cis-2-butene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
Isopentane	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
N-Pentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Trans-2-pentene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
1-Pentene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
Cis-2-pentene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS

Compound	Group	Analytical method
2,2-Dimethylbutane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Cyclopentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2,3-Dimethylbutane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2-Methylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
3-Methylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Isoprene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
1-Hexene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
n-Hexane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Methylcyclopentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2,4-Dimethylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Benzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
Cyclohexane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2-Methylhexane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2,3-Dimethylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
3-Methylhexane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2,2,4-Trimethylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
n-Heptane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Methylcyclohexane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
2,3,4-Trimethylpentane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Toluene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
2-Methylheptane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
3-Methylheptane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
n-Octane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Ethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
m/p-Xylene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
Styrene	Alkene	GC/GC/MS
o-Xylene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
n-Nonane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
Isopropylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
n-Propylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1-Ethyl-3- methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1-Ethyl-4-methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1,3,5-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1-Ethyl-2- methylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
n-Decane	Alkane	GC/GC/MS
1,2,3-Trimethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1,3-Diethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS
1,4-Diethylbenzene	Aromatic	GC/GC/MS

Compound	Group	Analytical method
Methanol	Alcohol	GC/GC/MS
Ethanol	Alcohol	GC/GC/MS
Isopropanol	Alcohol	GC/GC/MS
Formaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acetaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acrolein	Carbonyl	HPLC
Acetone	Carbonyl	HPLC
Propionaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Crotonaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Butyraldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Methacrolein	Carbonyl	HPLC
2-Butanone	Carbonyl	HPLC
Benzaldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC
Valeraldehyde	Carbonyl	HPLC

Carbonyls

We collected samples on DNPH cartridges and eluted and analyzed them using modifications of the methods of Uchiyama et al. (2009), Anneken et al. (2015), Shimadzu method LAAN-J-LC-E090 (Shimadzu, 2011), and Restek Lit. Cat. # EVSS2393A-UNV (Restek, 2018). These techniques are somewhat different from U.S. EPA Method TO-11A (EPA, 1999), which has become outdated due to improved instrumentation capabilities and column separation technologies. The sample path upstream of the cartridges was composed entirely of PFA Teflon with a PTFE filter upstream of the sample line to filter particles (5 µm pore size). Sample collection times were the same as those for the canisters described above (3 hours).

We eluted cartridges within 14 days of sampling and analyzed the eluent within 30 days. To elute DNPH cartridge samples, we flushed cartridges with 5 mL of a solution of 75% acetonitrile and 25% dimethyl sulfoxide (percent by volume). We collected the solution into 5 mL volumetric flasks and brought the flasks to a volume of 5 mL using 0.5–1 mL of the acetonitrile/dimethyl sulfoxide solution. Finally, we pipetted a 1.6 mL aliquot from the 5 mL flask into two 2 mL autosampler vials for analysis by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC). The second vial was kept as a spare in case of contamination or equipment failure.

We used a commercial standard mixture (M-1004; AccuStandard, New Haven, CT, USA) of derivatized carbonyls in acetonitrile for calibration. We analyzed samples with a Shimadzu (Somerset, NJ, USA) Nexera-i LC-2040C 3d Plus HPLC and a Shimadzu Shim-Pack Velox C18 column. We used a mixture of acetonitrile, tetrahydrofuran, and water as the eluent. We calibrated the instrument on each analysis day with a 5-point calibration curve and ran at least one additional calibration standard at the beginning and end of each analysis batch to check for retention time drift or other errors.

Additional information about the methods used is available in Lyman et al. (2021). Table 2 lists the organic compounds we measured.

Particulate Matter Measurements

We measured particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter smaller than 2.5 micrometers (PM_{2.5}) at Horsepool with a BAM 1020 monitor. We operated the instrument according to manufacturer protocols, with leak checks, flow and mass calibrations, detector calibrations, and cleanings performed at regular intervals. We obtained particulate matter values for other sites from the EPA AQS database (<https://aq5.epa.gov/api>).

Meteorological Measurements

We deployed solar radiation sensors at Horsepool (incoming and outgoing shortwave and longwave with a Hukseflux NR01 radiometer and UV-A and UV-B with Kipp and Zonen UV radiometers), Roosevelt (incoming and outgoing shortwave with a Kipp and Zonen CNR-4), and Castle Peak (incoming and outgoing shortwave and longwave with a Hukseflux NR01 radiometer). We check these sensors against calculations of clear-sky radiation annually.

We operated a suite of comprehensive, research-grade meteorological instruments at all sites operated by USU. We checked wind speed and direction, temperature, humidity, and barometric pressure against a NIST-traceable standard once annually. We checked snow depth sensors against a height standard annually. We also obtained meteorological data from the EPA AQS database.

Results and Discussion

Ozone

Very little snow cover existed across the lower elevations of the Uinta Basin, keeping ozone well below the 70 ppb EPA standard throughout winter 2023-24 at Horsepool (Figure 1) and at sites across the Basin (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Horsepool daily maximum ozone, average snow depth, and daytime average total UV radiation (incoming + reflected) during winter 2023-24. Inversion periods are shown as light blue boxes.

Figure 2. 8-hr average ozone from all sites listed in Table 2-1 during winter 2023-24.

Table 3 provides information about ozone observed at all monitoring stations in the Uinta Basin during winter 2023-24. No monitoring station experienced exceedances of the EPA ozone standard during the winter. An exceedance occurs when the daily maximum 8-hr average ozone value at a station is greater than the EPA standard of 70 ppb. The average of the fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone value over three consecutive calendar years is used to determine regulatory compliance with the standard.

Table 3. Eight-hour average ozone concentrations around the Uinta Basin, winter 2023-24.

	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	4 th Highest Daily Maximum	Number of Exceedances
Seven Sisters	26.1	47.5	6.9	44.5	0
Castle Peak	30.3	50.7	4.3	48.9	0
Dinosaur N.M.	26.4	50.3	4.9	48.1	0
Red Wash	28.4	44.8	9.5	42.8	0
Vernal	24.0	44.0	2.8	43.8	0
Whiterocks	32.0	49.3	5.5	48.0	0
Ouray	21.3	45.0	1.3	38.9	0
Roosevelt	22.7	46.8	0.0	45.9	0
Myton	24.6	47.8	0.4	46.8	0
Horsepool	28.1	48.3	7.5	45.7	0
Rangely	29.2	50.4	5.9	48.0	0

Figure 3 shows the spatial distribution of the fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone concentration around the Uinta Basin during winter 2023-24. All sites in the Basin exceeded the 70 ppb EPA ozone standard, but ozone tended to be lower at the Basin edges, in Whiterocks, Vernal, and Rangely. Ouray has typically had ozone in the same range as Horsepool and Seven Sisters, but this year Ouray had fewer exceedance days and lower ozone overall than those two sites. The reason for this is unclear.

Figure 3. Fourth-highest daily maximum 8-hr average ozone in the Uinta Basin during winter 2023-24. Monitoring stations are shown as red circles. Active oil and gas wells are shown as orange dots. The

background color indicates ozone concentration and was interpolated using the inverse distance weighting method in ArcGIS Pro.

There were some heavy snow events during winter 2023-24, but air temperatures were too high to support a snowpack after the heavy snowfall. One snowfall did lead to a weak inversion (where cold air begins to stagnate at the Basin floor, trapping pollution), but the snow melted before ozone levels built substantially. Snowfall and seasonal snowpack were substantial along both the Wasatch and Uinta Mountain ranges. Locals in the Basin noticed the contrast between the last two winters (see Figure 4); winter 2022-23 had snow cover across the entire Basin for months, leading to many inversion days and high ozone, in comparison to last winter with zero days of ozone.

Figure 4. Satellite images of the Uinta Basin from February 2023 and February 2024, showing the difference in snow cover across the two years. Images taken from <https://worldview.earthdata.nasa.gov/>.

Particulate Matter

PM_{2.5} concentrations stayed below the EPA standard of 35 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during winter 2023-24 at Vernal, Roosevelt, Rangely, and Horsepool (Figure 4-). As is typical of low-ozone winters in the Uinta Basin, PM_{2.5} was lower at Horsepool than at the other stations, where urban sources of particulate pollution dominate (Figure 5).

Figure 5. 24-hr average PM_{2.5} at monitoring stations around the Uinta Basin during winter 2023-24. The red-dashed line indicates the EPA PM_{2.5} standard.

Figure 6. Box-and-whisker plots of 24-hr average PM_{2.5} at four monitoring stations during winter 2023-24. X's indicate average values. Lines within the boxes indicate medians. Tops and bottoms of boxes indicate the third and first quartiles. Top and bottom whiskers indicate maximum and minimum values. Circles show outliers.

Comparison of Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak Data

The Horsepool and Roosevelt monitoring stations began operating in winter 2011-12 and were designed to contain nearly identical suites of instrumentation. At both stations we measure NO_x with instrumentation that doesn't bias NO₂ during winter inversion episodes, while all regulatory monitoring stations in the Uinta Basin use alternative, biased instrumentation. The

areas surrounding the Horsepool and Roosevelt stations are different from one another. The Horsepool station is on the northern edge of an area of dense oil and gas development (mostly gas), whereas the Roosevelt station is within a small city. Oil and gas development exists within and near the city of Roosevelt (mostly oil). The two stations are at very similar elevations (Table 1).

In 2017, Utah DAQ donated a NO_x analyzer that we upgraded with a photolytic converter and installed at our Castle Peak monitoring station. Castle Peak is in an area of dense oil development, and its elevation is less than 100 meters higher than the Roosevelt and Horsepool stations.

Figure 6 shows NO_x measured at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during winter 2023-24, and Figure 7 shows NO_z at Roosevelt and Horsepool. NO_x is the sum of NO and NO₂ which are important precursors to ozone production. NO_y (not shown in the figures) is the sum of NO_x and all other reactive nitrogen compounds (e.g., nitric and nitrous acids, organic nitrates, and particulate-bound nitrogen compounds). NO_z is the sum of all reactive nitrogen compounds except NO_x (in other words, it is NO_y minus NO_x). While NO_x is an ozone precursor, the compounds that comprise NO_z are mostly generated along with ozone because of photochemical reactions and are byproducts and indicators of atmospheric photochemical conditions.

Figure 7. Hourly average NO_x measured at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during winter 2023-24.

During winter 2023-24, as in previous winters, NO_x was higher in Roosevelt than at Horsepool and Castle Peak (Figure 6-) and was 4.0 times higher than Horsepool on average. NO_x in Roosevelt is emitted from urban sources like cars and home heating, as well as from oil and gas sources, while NO_x in the vicinity of Horsepool and Castle Peak originates almost entirely from oil and gas activity. NO_x at Castle Peak was 29% higher than Horsepool (p-value for a t-test of difference was <0.01). NO_z was 30% higher at Roosevelt than at Horsepool, indicating greater

photochemical activity at Roosevelt, especially in early winter when stagnant conditions with higher PM_{2.5} prevailed (Figure 7).

Figure 8. Hourly average NO₂ measured at Roosevelt and Horsepool during winter 2023-24.

NO_x at Roosevelt showed a pronounced peak in the morning and a lesser peak in the late afternoon and early evening, probably due to morning and afternoon peaks in local traffic (Figure 8-). Horsepool did not show a pronounced peak, probably because the majority of NO_x emissions at the site were due to stationary, continuous sources rather than traffic-related sources. Castle Peak showed a NO_x maximum in late morning, perhaps due to unique oil field traffic patterns.

Figure 9. Average NO_x at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during each hour of the day during inversion episodes that occurred during winter 2023-24. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals.

Methane was only 3% higher at Horsepool compared to Roosevelt. (Figure 9-), but average total non-methane hydrocarbons (TNMHC; measured as a single group of compounds with an in-situ hydrocarbon GC) were 61% higher at Roosevelt (Figure 10-). In the past, methane was much

higher at Horsepool and TNMHC was also higher, but new oil and gas activity near Roosevelt appears to be increasing emissions in the area.

Figure 10. Hourly average methane measured at Roosevelt and Horsepool during winter 2023-24. Well maintenance activity at the Horsepool site created interference until late December, and those data are not shown.

Figure 11. Hourly average total non-methane hydrocarbons (TNMHC) measured at Roosevelt and Horsepool during winter 2023-24. (ppmC is parts-per-million of carbon atoms.) Well maintenance activity at the Horsepool site created interference until late December, and those data are not shown. A spike of 55 ppmC occurred on 26 January at Roosevelt, and those data are not shown.

Snow depth was low, and snow cover was intermittent during the winter (Figure 11), keeping albedo (i.e., reflectivity from the ground surface) low (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Snow depth at the Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak stations during winter 2023-24.

Figure 13. Shortwave albedo at the Roosevelt and Castle Peak stations during winter 2023-24. Shortwave radiation is visible light from the sun. Albedo is the percentage of radiation that is reflected by the earth's surface.

Roosevelt ozone tended to be lower than at Horsepool and Castle Peak, especially at night (Figure 13). This was the case even though NO_x and non-methane hydrocarbons were both higher at Roosevelt than at Horsepool, and even though snow depth and albedo were similarly low at all sites. We expect that this occurred because the atmosphere at Roosevelt has more NO_x than is needed for ozone production. Too much NO_x can allow NO_x to react with and destroy ozone, suppressing ozone concentrations. At night, when no photochemistry occurs, ozone is not formed, but NO_x can still react with and destroy ozone, leading to the larger NO_x reduction at night in Roosevelt compared to the other locations.

Figure 14. Hourly average ozone measured at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during winter 2023-24.

Figure 15. Average ozone at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during each hour of the day during inversion episodes that occurred during winter 2023-24. Whiskers represent 95% confidence intervals.

Speciated Volatile Organic Compounds

This section focuses on measurements of individual organic compounds measured from whole air canister samples and DNPH cartridge samples.

As in previous years, organic compounds in the atmosphere at field sites were dominated by alkanes, especially lighter alkanes (Figure 15 and Figure 16-). Benzene, toluene, xylenes, and other aromatics were relatively low, and C8 and larger aromatics were rarely observed. The organic compound speciation at all sites was similar, indicating that the locations were all influenced by the same general source type (oil and natural gas production).

Figure 16. Percent by volume of measured organics at Castle Peak, Horsepool, and Roosevelt during winter 2023-24 comprised of alkanes, alkenes, aromatics, alcohols, and carbonyls.

Figure 17. Percent by volume of measured non-methane hydrocarbons at Castle Peak, Horsepool, and Roosevelt during winter 2023-24 comprised of compounds containing 2-9 carbon atoms (i.e., C2-C9; excludes alcohols and carbonyls).

Hydrocarbon concentrations at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak generally tracked each other and tended to be higher in early winter when atmospheric mixing was lower (Figure 17). Average total non-methane hydrocarbon, measured as the sum of individual compounds in units of ppbC, were similar at all sites ($p > 0.18$ for t-tests; Figure 18).

Figure 18. Time series of total non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHC) at Roosevelt, Horsepool, and Castle Peak during winter 2023-24. Units are parts per million of carbon atoms. Circles show the sum of speciated organic compounds derived from 3-hr canister measurements. Lines show 12-hour averages from continuously operating gas chromatographs.

Figure 19. Average total NMHC at Horsepool, Roosevelt, and Castle Peak. Values are the sum of individual compounds measured from canister samples in units of parts per million of carbon atoms. Whiskers show 95% confidence intervals.

Acknowledgments

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Summertime Air Quality

Seth Lyman, PhD

Three exceedances of the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) ozone standard of 70 ppb occurred during the spring and summer seasons in 2024 (1 April through 30 September). The maximum ozone during spring and summer occurred in Roosevelt (78 ppb on 22 July). Figure 1- shows a time series of ozone in the Basin during this period, and Table 1- shows a list of ozone values on exceedance days for the same stations. Some of these data are from EPA's real-time AirNowTech database, are not final, and may change.

Figure 1. 8-hr moving average ozone at monitoring stations in the Uinta Basin during summer 2024. The red dashed line shows the EPA ozone standard of 70 ppb.

Table 1. Daily maximum 8-hour average ozone for days during which ozone at at least one station exceeded the EPA standard for the period of 1 April through 30 September 2024.

	22-Jul	23-Jul	2-Aug
Myton	76	73	72
Ouray	66	61	57
Red Wash	71	71	64
Whiterocks	76	71	71
Roosevelt	78	73	69
Vernal	74	73	73

Figure 2 shows a time series of basin-wide daily maximum 8-hr average ozone along with basin-wide maximum PM_{2.5} for 1 April through 30 September 2024. Smoke emitted from fires is rich in PM_{2.5} (visible smoke is mostly PM_{2.5}). Figure 2- shows that PM_{2.5} increased to more than 35 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ on one day in September (the standard is for a 24-hr average), and that high PM_{2.5} days were sometimes (but not always) high ozone days.

Figure 2. Maximum ozone measured at any site in the Uinta Basin and Basin-average PM_{2.5} (average of Vernal and Roosevelt) for 1 April through 30 September 2024. All values are 8-hr moving averages. The EPA ozone standard of 70 ppb and the EPA PM_{2.5} standard of 35 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are also shown. The PM_{2.5} standard is for a 24-hr average.

Wildfire smoke can lead to ozone exceedances, but high PM_{2.5} from wildfire smoke does not always mean that ozone will also be high. The following figures show satellite images for the three ozone exceedance days during spring/summer 2024. The smoke observable in the figures on the exceedance days appears to have originated from wildfires distant from the Uinta Basin.

Figure 3. True-color satellite image from 22 July 2024. The Uinta Basin is highlighted in the blue box. Satellite-detected wildfires are shown as orange circles.

Figure 4. True-color satellite image from 23 July 2024. The Uinta Basin is highlighted in the blue box. Satellite-detected wildfires are shown as orange circles.

Figure 5. True-color satellite image from 2 August 2024. The Uinta Basin is highlighted in the blue box. Satellite-detected wildfires are shown as orange circles.

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Updates to Lab Spaces and Field Sites

Trevor O'Neil

Seth Lyman, PhD

In the past year, we have made significant improvements to both our laboratory spaces and field sites, optimizing our research capabilities and ensuring the continued high quality of our data collection.

Lab Consolidation and Equipment Surplus

Our lab spaces have been reorganized to enhance operational efficiency. We have combined similar analytical instruments into shared spaces to streamline maintenance, facilitate ease of use, and improve workflow. Additionally, a comprehensive review of our storage facilities identified obsolete or unused equipment, which are marked for surplus, freeing up valuable space for future acquisitions.

New Instrumentation Acquisitions

We purchased a new Agilent GCMS, at a significant academic discount. This advanced instrument replaces equipment that has been in service for over 14 years, offering improved accuracy and reliability in our analytical processes.

At our Castle Peak site, we installed a Teledyne N500 true NO₂/NO_x/NO analyzer replacing an outdated instrument. This new analyzer utilizes Cavity Attenuated Phase Shift (CAPS) Spectroscopy to measure true NO₂, NO_x, and NO gases. This method is known for its high sensitivity and accuracy while consuming minimal power and requiring significantly less upkeep compared to traditional chemiluminescence systems. Additionally, a new dilution calibrator has been installed at the same site to ensure the continued accuracy of our ongoing air quality measurements.

Field Site Management and QA/QC Enhancements

We have progressed in our efforts to update our field site management plan, particularly in quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC). This includes initiatives to simplify the data analysis process, with completion expected by mid-next year. The aim is to ensure that our field operations continue to align with best practices.

Uninterruptible Power Supply (UPS) Installation

To mitigate the risk of power outages, which have previously resulted in significant losses of both equipment and data, we installed an uninterruptible power supply (UPS) in the lab. This addition provides a critical buffer against the region's recurrent power disruptions, safeguarding our sensitive analytical instruments.

Collaboration with Utah Department of Air Quality (UDAQ)

We are appreciative of our partnership with the Utah Department of Air Quality (UDAQ). Over the past year, UDAQ has loaned us equipment, allowing us to continue uninterrupted data collection at our field sites while we await repairs and replacements for aging instruments. Additionally, we have acquired several surplus instruments from UDAQ allowing us to utilize these for improving instrumentation reliability and enabling higher data capture rates going forward.

Ongoing Research Collaborations

Our collaboration with UDAQ extends beyond equipment loans. We have also shared our expertise in programming for Campbell dataloggers, contributing to UDAQ's ongoing transition to digital data collection at their air quality monitoring sites. This knowledge exchange underscores the value of our continued partnership in advancing regional air quality research.

Special Project - Post-Storm Peak Design Improvements

With student involvement, we have initiated significant improvements to the dual-channel inlet design identified in research conducted at Storm Peak Observatory by a recently graduated master's student. We will test these updates to determine if they enhance our sampling capabilities, allowing the removal of the impactor from the flow path without compromising particulate filtration.

New Mercury Research Trailer

We have begun working on a new mercury (Hg) research trailer, which will support a collaborative project involving instrumentation from UNR, BYU, and USU. This trailer will play a key role in an upcoming study focused on mercury chemistry. A high school intern working for the research center this summer helped with the work, giving him exposure to some technical aspects of research which will help develop his skillset for future projects.

Training and Lab Relocation

We have continued to build expertise within our team, with two staff members receiving training on DNPH sample elutions needed in preparation for analysis using our Shimadzu HPLC. Additionally, our mercury analysis equipment was moved from Room 215 to Room 218, improving lab organization and efficiency in the use of gases and other resources.

Mobile Lab Trailer

The use of our mobile lab trailer to facilitate investigative research for pump jack engine enhancements provided an opportunity to work with the industry on improving fuel utilization by large engines in the oilfield. Our interest in this was to observe the improvements in fuel slip and its potential impact on emissions reduction.

Testing Heated Inlet Design for Field Measurement Stations

At cold temperatures, organic compounds may be retained on Teflon filters and tubing used for sample collection. We built two identical sample inlets at the Horsepool measurement station. Both inlets consisted of a PFA Teflon filter housing with a 5 μm pore size PTFE Teflon filter, followed by PFA tubing leading into our measurement trailer. The tubing led to a flow-restricting orifice and a vacuum pump to provide continuous flushing of the line. A tee upstream of the orifice led to whole-air sampling canisters for collection of organic compound samples. We insulated one of the inlets and heated it to 25°C, and we left the other inlet unheated. We collected three pairs of heated and unheated samples and analyzed them as described in the section of this report that discusses wintertime air quality.

Winter temperatures were mild during 2023-24, which may have led to smaller differences between the heated and unheated inlets. Samples were collected on the mornings of 14 February, 20 February, and 13 March, and the average ambient air temperatures during each sampling period were 4.9, 2.5, and 0.3°C, respectively. Figure 1 shows the average difference between organic compound concentration results for samples collected on the heated and unheated lines. As the figure shows, results were higher for most compounds on the heated line, which may indicate that the unheated line retained organics. Compounds that were higher, on average, in the unheated line included 2-methylpentane, methylcyclopentane, benzene, cyclohexane, and 2-methylhexane. The differences were small, however, for all compounds (average \pm standard deviation of $2 \pm 5\%$). For reference, individual compound differences in replicate analyses of the same samples were $1 \pm 7\%$ (average \pm standard deviation) during winter 2023-24.

Though the differences between the heated and unheated lines were similar to differences among replicate analyses of the same samples, we decided that the best practice for the future would be to heat organic compound sampling inlets at our field sites. We have installed heated inlets for all organic compound sampling (including carbonyls) for the 2024-25 winter at Horsepool, Castle Peak, and Roosevelt.

Figure 1. The percent difference between organic concentrations from the heated and unheated sample inlet lines, organized by order of elution during gas chromatographic analysis of the collected air samples (x axis). Only compounds with results above the method detection limit are shown.